

Lost in Translation:

Text and Context in Economic versus Legal Concepts of the Contract

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Abstract

We examine the epistemic disjunction between economic and legal scholarship with respect to the concept of the contract. While economics continues to tend to treat the “contract” as a single, unified concept, legal studies, increasingly, acknowledges wide institutional variation in contracts in different contexts. Based on extensive analysis of the empirical evidence on contracting practices, we take a radical step in the direction of challenging a unitary theory of contract. We propose that there exist patterns of contracting across three different sectors: the high, medium and low levels of sophistication of the market economy and tease out, so far unnoticed, similarities in the high and low ends of the spectrum, i.e., instances where uncertainty is particularly salient. We argue that economic theory would provide a more accurate analysis of contracting practices, and, indeed, contracts, if these different variations, and their implications, were foregrounded.

1. Introduction

Contracts have long been a preoccupation of economic theory. A central focus of New Institutional Economics, in particular, has been the importance of legal institutions and social norms for economic activity, and specifically the role of contracts in facilitating exchange in the market.

Standard economic theory typically treats the “contract” as if it represented a single, unified legal concept, easily definable across different jurisdictions and different sectors of the market economy – amenable to a generalized economic analysis. The notion of a unified concept of contract is based on the premise that contractual obligations are molded by the parties themselves, typically in the form of a written agreement, and enforced more or less mechanically by courts. Within this narrative, the “law of contract”, as developed within legal scholarship, is, at best, ancillary; the rules of a contract allocate risks between the parties and the law of contract focuses mostly on determining what promises should be enforced and the remedies for breaking such enforceable promises.

Glossing over the potential institutional variations available in contract law, economics narrows down the concept of “contract” to this simplified version—a more or less perfect expression of the autonomous will of the parties— and then mostly focuses on the subject of “contractual design”, perhaps only indirectly providing normative considerations for contract law.¹ Contractual design focuses, then, on how the parties to a transaction might create governance structures that would be more suited to diminishing transaction costs in different contractual settings. Notably, Williamson, whose work on contractual governance is seminal, proposes a scheme to classify contractual transactions and to determine which institutional framework would suit them best.²

In this article we claim that there is an epistemic imbalance between economic and legal studies in the use of the term “contract” that goes largely unrecognised in the literature. What economists consider to be a contract represents a distorted and imprecise picture of the jurists’ understanding of the concept of contract. This claim has concrete implications for the economic analysis of contracts: there are different models of contract law available, which are salient in identifying what is the most economically efficient way to organize collaboration in the market.³ In the past 150 years, there has been a growing recognition in legal studies that a market economy does not have a single institutional form⁴, but, rather, can be supported by different forms of contract law. In other words, there is no single model of contract law that derives from a market economy: important differences might subsist, significantly altering the economic understanding of the potential market exchange. These insights must be brought to bear on the economic analysis of contracts and may help to make the case for a new paradigm in law and economics that draws more equally from the two disciplines.

This article makes two distinct contributions. First, we analyze how this epistemic disconnection has been established and how more recent studies on contracting practices represent an even more radical step in deepening the diverging perspectives between economic and legal studies on the concept of contract, providing extensive empirical evidence that refutes a unitary contract theory. Second, we argue that there are important similarities, so far largely unnoticed, between contractual practices in the high end of sophistication of the market economy and practices in

¹ R Scott & G Triantis, *Incomplete Contracts and the Theory of Contract Design*, 56 CASE WEST. RESERVE LAW REV. 187–201, 188 (2005).

² OE Williamson, *Transaction-Cost Economics: The Governance of Contractual Relations*, 22 J. LAW ECON. 233–261, 234 (1979).

³ R Gilson, C Sabel & R Scott, *Text and Context: Contract Interpretation as Contract Design*, 100 CORNELL LAW REV. 23–98 (2014); D Wielsch, *Contract interpretation regimes*, 81 MOD. LAW REV. 958 (2018).

⁴ RM UNGER, WHAT SHOULD LEGAL ANALYSIS BECOME? 45 (1996).

the low end of sophistication of the market economy. One of our main insights is to reveal these similarities and explore their implications.

We structure our argument as follows. The following two sections are theoretical. The first of the two substantiates the claim that economic theory presents a highly reductive perspective of contract law, while the next one presents the contrasting perspective of comparative contract law, evidencing a continuing conflict between textualism and contextualism in contract theory, with different approaches to striking the balance between these two tendencies. In other words, there is a constant tug-of-war between freedom of contract and solidarity in contract law, often resulting in potentially conflicting interpretations of agreements by the courts. These two sections evidence the robust theoretical divergence between law and economics on the epistemological understanding of contract.

We then turn to recent empirical evidence, underscoring the fact that this disconnection has become more radical due to the emergence of new contracting practices in the market economy. In section four, we review the empirical literature on collaboration in the market economy, proposing that the “knowledge economy” represents a decisive break from the orthodox economic understanding of contract. We make this claim on the basis of having assembled one of the most comprehensive existing databases on contracting practices, drawing on both primary and secondary sources. We suggest that a pattern emerges from examining the empirical evidence in three different sectors: the mid, the high and the low levels of sophistication of the market economy. Finally, in section five, we present our conclusions on the analysis of the empirical evidence. The empirical data robustly supports the assertion that, even within a single legal system, the concept of the contract and the contractual practices will vary according to the level of market sophistication involved. Furthermore, we find some unexpected similarities between contracting practices in the high and low end of sophistication of the market economy, i.e., whenever the contractual framework has to grapple with a high level of uncertainty.

2. Economics’ reductive interpretation of the “contract”

Within the dominant paradigm of economics, known as neoclassicism, the functioning of the economy is modelled on the basis of a series of assumptions meant to represent abstractions from reality that render it more methodologically tractable, typically for quantitative analysis. This tendency towards boiling down often complex realities to stylized representations as a heuristic device is central to its epistemic approach. So, for instance, as Bowles and Carlin show, traditional neoclassical economics largely assumes that information is complete and verifiable, competition

is perfect, the sole evaluative criterion for the functioning of the economy is Pareto-efficiency, i.e., the exhaustion of all possible gains from trade or exchange, and that the system is largely self-stabilizing.⁵ Most crucially, for present purposes, the economy is characterized as being populated by the materialistic, far-sighted, all-knowing and atomistic *homo economicus* of rational choice theory, interacting in a context where all social interaction is defined by buying and selling in the market. Furthermore, fundamental determinants of physical constraints on the economy—like nature and technology—are external to the model, as are accounts of power and agent heterogeneity. Finally, the State, depicted as a Marshall-Pigou style auctioneer, is trivially assumed to perform the necessary coordination functions for the economy.

This epistemic frame has, famously, led to a series of oversimplifications of various kinds, not least in its interpretation of the concept of the contract. Indeed, in the wake of the institutional revolution in economics—both the Law and Economics movement led by the Chicago school and New Institutional Economics—law has come to be regarded as something of an economic panacea. Indeed, the significance of the “rule of law” for economic growth has been stressed by any number of highly influential studies ranging from the World Bank’s World Governance Indicators⁶ to the La-Porta, Lopez de Silanes, Shleifer and Vishny’s legal origins hypothesis⁷ to Acemoglu, Johnson and Robinson’s treatise on “why nations fail”⁸, but this is largely reduced to the two institutions of private property and contracts. The portrayal of contracts on this account is, however, almost a parody: not only are they traditionally assumed to be complete, but also enforceable at no extra cost.

The intuition behind the emphasis on the institutions of property, and particularly, contract is straightforward: economic process is based on maximizing gains from trade (going all the way back to the Ricardian logic of comparative advantage) and the role of these institutions, at their core, is considered to be to minimize uncertainty and incentivize mutually beneficial exchange. The lens through which mainstream economics has typically analysed contracts is that of a principal-agent problem: the agent is deputed by the principal to execute certain tasks, but the monitoring of the agent’s actions by the principal is, at best, imperfect. The main function of contracts within this rubric is to overcome what economists refer to as the problems of “moral

⁵ S Bowles and W Carlin, “What Students Learn in Economics 101: Time for a Change”, *Journal of Economic Literature* (forthcoming).

⁶ See <https://info.worldbank.org/governance/wgi/>.

⁷ R La Porta et al., *Law and Finance*, 106 J. POLIT. ECON. 1113–1155 (1998).

⁸ D Acemoglu, S Johnson & JA Robinson, *The Colonial Origins of Comparative Development: An Empirical Investigation: Reply*, 102 AM. ECON. REV. 3077–3110 (2012); D Acemoglu, S Johnson & JA Robinson, *Reversal of Fortune: Geography and Institutions in the Making of the Modern World Income Distribution*, 117 Q. J. ECON. 1231–1294 (2002).

hazard” (the fact that the agent may act disingenuously due to the nature of risk sharing between the parties) and “adverse selection” (the fact that the agent’s entry into the contract may, itself, be based on an element of deceit), but this assumes *ex-ante* a relationship of significant mistrust between contracting parties and an adversarial tone. The overwhelming emphasis with the elimination or mitigation of uncertainty yields the notion that the clearer and more unambiguous the text of the mythical complete contract—specifying the legal consequences of all possible contingencies—the more optimal the economic outcomes it will lead to, irrespective of context. This fails to take account of the fact that apart from being an impossibility, a complete contract may not create the optimal collaborative ethos or, worse still, actively destroy it. The knee-jerk reaction of neoclassical economics is to prioritize text over context, individual autonomy over social solidarity, formality over informality and rigidity over flexibility.

Specifically, the fetishization of contracts within economics began with the publication of Coase’s *The Problem of Social Cost*, the foundational text of Chicago-style law and economics, as late as 1960. Coase was concerned with “discovering the effects of varying the legal position on the working of the economic system”⁹ making contracts central to his analysis:

“In order to carry out a market transaction it is necessary to discover who it is that one wishes to deal with, inform people that one wishes to deal and on what terms, to conduct negotiations leading up to a bargain, to draw up the contract, to undertake the inspection needed to make sure that the terms of the contract are being observed and so on.”¹⁰

Coase’s seminal scholarship profoundly changed economics’ engagement with law. It introduced the notion of “transaction costs” into economic thought, which had been, until then, a fundamental omission, missing the main motive engine behind economic growth and development: the continual drive to reduce the costs associated with the process of exchange. The economic takeaway that follows from Coase’s insight is straightforward: the more easily and costlessly parties to a contract can transact the better. It is worth noting, however, that this need not, necessarily, be by means of a stringent formal agreement.

The emphasis on formal contracts comes from what has come to be known as the “Coase Theorem”: “[I]f transaction costs are assumed to be zero and the rights of various parties well

⁹ R COASE, *THE FIRM, THE MARKET AND THE LAW* 28 (1990); the article was first published, however, as R. H. Coase, *The Problem of Social Cost*, 3 J. LAW ECON. 1–44 (1960).

¹⁰ COASE, *supra* note 9 at 6–7; see further pp 114; Dahlman (1979) crystallized the concept of transaction costs by describing them as “search and information costs, bargaining and decision costs, policing and enforcement costs.” CJ Dahlman, *The Problem of Externality*, 22 J. LAW ECON. 141–162 (1979).

defined, the allocation of resources would be the same [irrespective of which of the two parties the rights are assigned to].”¹¹ Although a faithful interpretation of the Coase Theorem is that economic efficiency is maximized if rights over all relevant attributes of economic activity can be defined at low transaction costs, it is popularly interpreted to mean that as long as property rights are clearly assigned, the result will be economically efficient irrespective of which party the rights are assigned to. Coase made a decisive break from legal intuition by characterizing the “bundle of rights” as a tradeable commodity: arguing that if rights could be transacted, then they would be acquired by the party for whom they have the most economic value and, further, rights could be divided so as to bring about the most economically valuable combination.¹²

Coasian analysis made contract unprecedentedly foundational to our understanding of markets, first within Law and Economics and, then, as the movement gained ground, within economics as a whole and the widespread interpretation of the Coase Theorem made clarity of contract a matter of paramount importance. Indeed, he argued that the characteristic feature of markets, ranging from the medieval markets to the modern-day stock exchange, has been the provision of security and the means for settlement of disputes, “an intricate system of rules and regulation” – more specifically, the protection of private property and, crucially, the enforcement of contracts.¹³ When markets were relatively small and localized, these rules could be provided privately, but under less contained conditions the provision of a private regulatory system would be very difficult and the State legal system would have to be relied upon.¹⁴ The cumulative impact of the Law and Economics movement was to make legal rules deferential to one goal and one goal alone: increasing economic efficiency.

The work of Posner particularly in *An Economic Analysis of Law*, published in 1973, extended this mode of thinking to law in general—applying economic analysis to a range of doctrinal areas ranging from torts to criminal law—making the efficiency of rules the chief criterion for their evaluation.¹⁵ Becker, another key exponent of the law and economics tradition, extended the analysis to topics like family organization, fertility and racial discrimination.¹⁶ At the macro-level,

¹¹ COASE, *supra* note 9 at 13.

¹² *Id.* at 12.

¹³ *Id.* at 9.; other theorists have also stressed the economic importance of property rights – for instance, Demsetz (1967). He argues that property rights are crucial for the proper functioning of markets – contending that market failure is most likely in cases of commonly or publicly owned property. He stresses two key characteristics of private property that are conducive to the efficiency of markets – that it promotes efficient decision-making about property and allows responsibility for use of property to be more readily attributed. H Demsetz, *Toward a Theory of Property Rights*, 57 AM. ECON. REV. 347–359 (1967).

¹⁴ COASE, *supra* note 9 at 10.

¹⁵ R POSNER, *ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF LAW* (1972).

¹⁶ See, for instance, GS BECKER, *A TREATISE ON THE FAMILY* (1981).

North's work, seminal in the New Institutional Economics literature, established that as nations become increasingly specialized in the wake of global economic development, the gains that will accrue to a nation from trade will depend on reducing transaction costs, thus "whether a nation progresses towards growth, stagnation or decline" will depend on its institutions, and, in particular, its contractual regime.¹⁷

Various of the assumptions within the neoclassical paradigm—complete information, the rational actor, complete contracts—trivialize the complex legal institutions that contracts are and the excessive focus on certainty, completely and formality limited their potential to aid innovation. Indeed, it was only with Hart's scholarship, at the cutting edge of the contracts literature, that in the 1980s and 1990s mainstream economics started to seriously acknowledge the possibility of incomplete contracts and to shift away from the Coasian consensus. It did so, however, in Hart's early scholarship, largely in terms of "residual control rights" within the paradigm of what came to be referred to as Property Rights Theory (PRT).¹⁸ The central concern of this theory was with hold up problems (the fear that one party will be held up by another) and the role of physical ownership of assets in overcoming these, but it located itself firmly within the mould of conventional principal-agent analysis. It was not until much later that the idea of shading emerged from this body of scholarship treating contracts as types of reference points – mechanisms or means of continually aligning expectations as unexpected events occur or needs change over time – introduces greater nuance into the economic concept of the contract.¹⁹ It distinguishes between "perfunctory" (complying with the letter of the contract) and consummate (doing justice to the spirit of the contract) performance, and identifies that the nature of cooperation and collaboration between parties to a contract relies on iteration and a sense of contentment on the part of active collaborators.

Hart's most recent scholarship builds on this idea²⁰, and borrows significantly – and explicitly – from legal notions of the contract (as will be discussed in the penultimate section). But, even in Hart's work, the main thrust of the work has treated incompleteness as a shortcoming to be overcome, and a derogation from the ability to achieve maximal efficiency.

¹⁷ DC NORTH, INSTITUTIONS, INSTITUTIONAL CHANGE AND ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE 97 (1991).

¹⁸ O Hart & J Moore, *Property Rights and the Nature of the Firm*, 98 J. POLIT. ECON. 1119–1158 (1990).

¹⁹ O Hart & J Moore, *Contracts as Reference Points*, CXXIII Q. J. ECON. 1–48 (2008).

²⁰ D Frydinger, O Hart & K Vitasek, *A New Approach to Contracts*, HARVARD BUSINESS REVIEW, 2019.

3. Genealogy of Contract Law: the continuing tug-of-war between textualism and contextualism

The tenor of the debate for legal scholars is different from that of their counterparts in economics. A long-standing legal genealogy robustly challenges the unitary concept of contract, presenting variations of rules and methods of interpretation in contract law across different legal systems and different segments of the market economy, even within a single legal system.²¹ Furthermore, despite the existence of different theoretical approaches to contract law, none of them has been able to claim predominance. Normative approaches, often based on a single norm, such as autonomy or efficiency, face difficulties in explaining the particular requirements of different contractual settings; pluralist approaches, balancing the existence of different values to assess contracts (such as good faith, reliance, freedom of contract, efficiency), have been unable to articulate a meta-principle to solve the conflict between these different principles when they collide. The central debate within legal scholarship focuses, instead, on the relative importance of “text” (terms explicitly and voluntarily agreed by parties) and “context” (terms read into the agreement) in determining what constitutes the contract.²²

Different genealogies of private law and, more specifically, contract law, have been elaborated in the course of the last few decades. While there is some variation in the narratives, most of them present the same central elements: most accounts, both in the common and civil law traditions (albeit with significant differences), abandon the 19th century notion of classical contract law, focused exclusively on the concept and rules of contract as a derivation of the parties’ will, in favour of a more “social law” in the 20th century.²³ In this “social law”, to different degrees, considerations *beyond* the parties’ will are taken into account when analyzing contract liability, such as reliance, legitimate expectations, good faith, reasonableness and other social purposes established in distinct legal documents. The titles of seminal works in the field—the “rise and fall of freedom of contract”²⁴ or the “death of contract”²⁵ in the sense of embodying exclusively the meeting of minds’ of the parties — provide a flavor of this shift in thinking. At the same time, this

²¹ A Schwartz & R Scott, *Contract Theory and the Limits of Contract Law*, 113 YALE LAW J. 541–619, 543 (2003): “Contract law has neither a complete descriptive theory, explaining what the law is, nor a complete normative theory, explaining what the law should be. These gaps are unsurprising given the traditional definition of contract as embracing all promises that the law will enforce. Even a theory of contract law that focuses only on the enforcement of bargains must still consider the entire continuum from standard form contracts between firms and consumers to commercial contracts among businesses.”

²² Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 3 at 25 et seq.

²³ F WIEACKER, *A HISTORY OF PRIVATE LAW IN EUROPE: WITH PARTICULAR REFERENCE TO GERMANY* (T Weir tran., 1st edn ed. 1996).

²⁴ PS ATIYAH, *THE RISE AND FALL OF FREEDOM OF CONTRACT* (1979).

²⁵ G GILMORE, *DEATH OF CONTRACT* (RKL Collins ed., 2 ed. 1995).

narrative of the rise of the social or the decline of contract has, to different degrees depending on the jurisdiction, encountered critics seeking to minimize or circumscribe the influence of this “social approach”, resorting instead to a neoclassical perspective.²⁶ This line of thought has claimed that the parties’ autonomy remains the cornerstone of contract law, and mere corrections should be undertaken to minimize unjust results. Indeed, this position comes closest to the economists’ view of the contract presented in the last section.

This battle remains alive. In the US, “textualists” and “contextualists” both claim predominance.²⁷ In Continental Europe, proponents of private autonomy complain of hypertrophy of general principles of good faith²⁸ and other social constructs, while others defend the importance of protecting social values in European private law.²⁹ In the UK, there is a recurring discussion about the role, and the extent of influence, that the concept of good faith could play/exert in contract law.³⁰ Others, still, attempt to synthesize classical and social law elements, claiming that these different interests, both liberal and social, coexist in different ways in different contexts, and are considerations to be balanced in each case, with an emergent discussion on the importance of the principle of proportionality in private law.³¹

It is difficult to make a definitive pronouncement on the outcome of this debate. The dominant position varies significantly, depending on both the jurisdiction and the domain of contract law. It is important to note, however, that, in most jurisdictions, parties’ autonomy is given special significance in the context of commercial transactions, involving sophisticated parties with expertise and legal assistance, who, arguably, would reject having a court intervening and making decisions on their behalf. In Continental Europe, on the whole, the principle of parties’ autonomy has, to a large extent, given way to a contract law based on examining the legitimate expectations of the parties.³² In the UK, more so than in the rest of Europe, there are claims that what prevails is a contract law based on the parties’ autonomy, now opposed by an extensive emerging literature on good faith and relational contracts.³³ In the US, there seems to be no prevailing

²⁶ C FRIED, *CONTRACT AS PROMISE: A THEORY OF CONTRACTUAL OBLIGATION* (2015); J MORGAN, *CONTRACT LAW MINIMALISM: A FORMALIST RESTATEMENT OF COMMERCIAL CONTRACT LAW* (2013).

²⁷ Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 3 at 25 et seq.

²⁸ C Jamin, *Quelle nouvelle crise du contrat?*, in *LA NOUVELLE CRISE DU CONTRAT* 7 (C Jamin, & D Mazeaud eds., 2003).

²⁹ M HESSELINK, *CFR & SOCIAL JUSTICE* (2008).

³⁰ See chapter 21 in N ANDREWS, *CONTRACT LAW* 588 et seq (2015).

³¹ D Kennedy, *A transnational genealogy of proportionality in Private Law*, in *FOUNDATIONS OF EUROPEAN PRIVATE LAW* 185–219 (R Brownsword et al. eds., 2011).

³² R ZIMMERMAN & S WHITTAKER, *GOOD FAITH IN EUROPEAN CONTRACT LAW* 700 (2000).

³³ H Collins, *Is a relational contract a legal concept?*, in *CONTRACT IN COMMERCIAL LAW* 37–59 (S Degeling, J Edelman, & J Goudkamp eds., 2016); D Campbell, *Good Faith and the Ubiquity of the ‘Relational’ Contract*, 77 *MOD. LAW REV.* 475–492 (2014).

position, but different schools of thought and authors presenting different views (new private law³⁴, law & economics³⁵, critical legal studies³⁶, relational contract law³⁷, braiding theory³⁸, among others). What is noteworthy, however, is that by comparison with economics the “social” perspective is an influential position in legal theory in almost all key jurisdictions.

Of particular significance in dislodging the centrality of a unitary perspective of contract has been Macneil’s theory of relational contracts, underscoring the existence of a range of contracting relationships falling somewhere in between the two ideal poles fetishized by the literature, where either more formal or more relational (or contextual) forms of contract law would prevail. Macneil sought to develop a taxonomy on the three distinct phases of contemporary contract law: classical, neoclassical and relational.³⁹ These would coexist within a particular contract law system, governing different kinds of transactions.

According to MacNeil, classical contract law is based on the paradigm of a one-time exchange contract, seen as a discrete transaction, separated and isolated from its context. The agreement is considered to be entirely contained within the express terms included by the parties themselves with any further external consideration being treated as extraneous. Neoclassical contract law strikes a middle ground, acknowledging that the contract, especially in long-term relationships, cannot accurately predict and solve all future contingencies. It envisages that to deal with these difficulties, parties might insert specially tailored clauses into their agreements.⁴⁰ Moreover, the legal doctrine provides courts with the ability to intervene exceptionally in limited situations (e.g. through the doctrines of frustration, impossibility, good faith, among others). This perspective, therefore, gives primacy to the notion of private autonomy, but in exceptional situations, allows for court intervention. Macneil then introduces the paradigm of relational contracts.⁴¹ Within this rubric, a contractual relationship can be inserted at different points along a spectrum that ranges from discrete contracts to relational contracts. Some relationships, especially one-time spot exchange contracts, are closer to the discrete pole with the formal

³⁴ JCP Goldberg, *Introduction: Pragmatism and Private Law*, 125 HARV. LAW REV. 1640–1663 (2012).

³⁵ See ch 13 in STEVEN SHAVELL, *FOUNDATIONS OF ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF LAW* (2004).

³⁶ D Kennedy, *From the Will Theory to the Principle of Private Autonomy: Lon Fuller’s Consideration and Form*, 100 COLUMBIA LAW REV. 94 (2000).

³⁷ IR MACNEIL, *THE NEW SOCIAL CONTRACT: AN INQUIRY INTO MODERN CONTRACTUAL RELATIONS* (1980).

³⁸ RJ Gilson, CF Sabel & RE Scott, *Braiding: the Interaction of Formal and Informal Contracting in Theory, Practice, and Doctrine*, 110 COLUMBIA LAW REV. 1377–1447 (2010).

³⁹ IR Macneil, *Contracts: Adjustment of Long-Term Economic Relations under Classical, Neoclassical, and Relational Contract Law*, 72 NORTHWEST. UNIV. LAW REV. 854–902 (1977).

⁴⁰ Among the mechanisms that the parties themselves can include, it is possible to identify mechanisms for the adjustment of prices by nominated third parties or the reference to external bodies establishing updated reference values for certain products, for instance.

⁴¹ Macneil, *supra* note 39 at 890.

contract rules serving as the guiding norms. Other relationships, i.e., long-term agreements involving a significant degree of cooperation, are closer to the relational pole. At this relational end, it is more difficult to predict future contingencies, there is greater uncertainty and the parties' relationship and expectations acquire greater importance in interpreting the contract. In this relational pole, the rules of classical or neoclassical contract law are insufficient to deal with the arising contingencies. There is a need for further development. Macneil claimed that it was the task of the legal system and legal rules themselves to develop a framework that could serve to favor cooperation in this highly relational and uncertain environment: in other words, a more contextualist perspective on contract law.

Macneil's theory, however, remained markedly abstract and unable to propose a more elaborate taxonomy of contract transactions. Despite efforts to specify the features of a relational contract⁴², it refrained from articulating in legal detail how contract rules or methods of interpretation should differ for specific kinds of transactions or sectors of the market economy. For that reason, Eisenberg claimed that "there is no law of relational contracts", but rather specific kinds of contracts that become so embedded in a specific reality and relationship between the contractual partners that they require tailored solutions.⁴³ Macneil's relational contract theory succeeded, however, in graphically highlighting the shortcomings of a single concept of contract.

The scepticism regarding the unitary concept of contract, in this sense, is growing. Unger (2015) aptly describes the problems of such an approach:

First, there are the exclusions: whole areas of law, such as family law, labor law, antitrust, corporate law, and even international law, which were once regarded as branches of unified contract theory but gradually came to be seen as requiring categories unassimilable to that theory. Then there are the exceptions: bodies of law and social practice such as fiduciary relationships that come under an anomalous set of principles within the central area of contract. Finally, there are the repressions: problems such as those of long-term contractual dealings that, though resistant to the solutions provided by a theory oriented primarily toward the one-shot, arm's-length, and low-trust transaction, are nevertheless more often dealt with by ad hoc deviations from the dominant rules and ideas than by clearly distinct norms.⁴⁴

⁴² IR MacNeil, *The Many Futures of Contracts*, 47 SOUTH. CALIF. LAW REV. 691–816, 744 ff (1973).

⁴³ MA Eisenberg, *Why There Is No Law of Relational Contracts*, 94 NORTHWEST. UNIV. LAW REV. 805–821 (1999).

⁴⁴ RM UNGER, *THE CRITICAL LEGAL STUDIES MOVEMENT: ANOTHER TIME, A GREATER TASK* 143–144 (2015).

In the next section, we advance the claim that the most recent contracts scholarship in this genealogy represents a further—and more radical—step in this process of disintegration of a unitary contract theory. Based on empirical evidence, it has become possible to devise a more developed picture of the variation of contracting practices across the market economy and the law and methods of interpretation applicable to them, giving unprecedented substance to the claim that the “Law of Contract” and contractual practices are not unitary across the market economy.

4. The empirical perspective: the pluralism of contract across the market economy

In the previous section, we suggested that legal scholarship takes a more nuanced view of contracts than economics, which sees it as a closed, single concept. In the legal realm, instead, there is a range of different forms to institutionalize contract rules, each displaying a different balance between textualism and contextualism (or between contractual autonomy and social solidarity). As a consequence, legal systems might impart different degrees of importance to the formal agreement concluded by the contractual parties.

In the recent legal scholarship, two contributions have sought to identify different sector-specific forms of contract interpretation and levels of support for private orderings. Gilson, Sabel & Scott have divided contractual relationships according to the level of uncertainty and the scale of the market.⁴⁵ Wielsch has claimed that contract interpretation should differentiate between interpretative methods that are institution-preserving, where legal institutions have already sufficient knowledge about the parties’ transactions and are able to interpret them according to established standards, and those that are institution-creating, where the parties through contract practices create their own regime of interpretation and institutional context.⁴⁶ In these works, however, there is no extensive analysis of the existing empirical studies on contractual collaboration and how they fit within the proposed categories. Furthermore, some of those contractual transactions that we consider to fall in the low-level of sophistication of the market economy are mostly bypassed by these articles, thereby missing an important dimension of the analysis.

While the question of the appropriate balance between text and context has long been contested, empirical evidence may prove the tie breaker in the theoretical argument on the

⁴⁵ Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 3.

⁴⁶ Wielsch, *supra* note 3.

accuracy of the unitary notion of contract. We argue that empirical evidence supports the claim that, even within the same legal system, in the domain of contract law, the degree of importance given to the formal contract varies significantly according to the sector of the economy involved. In none of the sectors is the “sanctity” of the formal agreement entirely upheld by the legal system⁴⁷; but, in some areas, it might be significantly more decisive than others. This institutional variation is clearly observable in empirical studies.

To analyse this variation, we have drawn on both primary and secondary sources to construct one of the most comprehensive empirical databases in existence on contracting practices in the market economy, dividing them in three different sectors: the high, mid and low-level of sophistication of the market economy. We use the following criteria as indicators of the level of market complexity/sophistication: high accumulation of capital, complexity of knowledge and technology employed, the productivity or efficiency of production involved in the underlying activity (understood as the ratio between the output produced given the inputs required) and the extent to which the system of production is based on constant innovation. What seems to define the ideal case of market sophistication, however, is the creation of new markets by companies innovating, often eking out a market that was not foreseeable under the previous consumer demand.⁴⁸ Indeed, it is the companies producing disruptive innovation that have been hailed by business studies as the most advanced companies in the world.

In each of these sectors, a distinct picture emerges, with different contracting practices, distinct degrees of importance given to the formal terms and different degrees of contract enforcement applied to solve potential disputes. We start by examining the contracting practices within the mid-level of sophistication of the market economy, perhaps the domain in which the traditional neoclassical perspective of the role of contract law remains the most accurate in the practice.

a. Mid-level sophistication in the market

The mid-level of sophistication includes perhaps the most emblematic relationships of the market economy: mostly commercial relationships between firms (unlike consumer or commercial

⁴⁷ Contextualism claims that the understanding of the contract itself depends fundamentally on grasping the context, the ‘implicit understandings’ that can provide particular meanings for relationships in different sectors of the economy and amid distinct contracting communities. H Collins, *Introduction: The Research Agenda of Implicit Dimensions of Contracts*, in *IMPLICIT DIMENSIONS OF CONTRACT: DISCRETE, RELATIONAL AND NETWORK CONTRACTS*, 8–9 (H Collins, D Campbell, & J Wightman eds., 2003).

⁴⁸ On the concept of disruptive innovation, through which companies deploy new markets, see CM CHRISTENSEN, *THE INNOVATOR’S DILEMMA: WHEN NEW TECHNOLOGIES CAUSE GREAT FIRMS TO FAIL* (3rd ed ed. 2016).

relationships between private parties, involving a low level of sophistication), often employing the average, or standard, technological and organizational practices in their activities. Standard examples of industries in this sector include agriculture, mining, manufacturing and services and, typically, contracts that do not involve a high degree of uncertainty (instances such as the sale or supply of cotton, diamonds, grains, different kinds of clearly specified machines or services have been explored in the literature). The mere fact that a particular production process or product/service embeds some technology does not qualify it as representative of the high-level of sophistication. A contract for the supply of software, for instance, where one company is simply providing the contractual partner with a reasonably well defined product, without the expectation of having to pursue continuous innovation in its development and improvement, is one that may well fit within the mid-level of complexity of the market. As there is no need to pursue radical innovation, which would require significant capital, sophisticated workforce, development of frontier technology, but simply a technology that has already been developed, there is not much difference from a simple contractual relationship to supply footwear or cotton. At the same time, the supply of an agricultural product, such as soy or grains, may be developed through a highly sophisticated technological process, for instance, requiring the co-creation of drones to be used in precision agriculture, which involve advanced levels of technology and would fit the high-level of sophistication of the market economy.

The contractual relationships typical of mid-level of sophistication of the market economy hold significant financial importance, as they often involve a transaction between firms of relevant scale, considering the quantity of output produced/supplied. Nonetheless, they do not reach the highest levels of innovation, productivity and competitiveness of the vanguard of companies in the “knowledge economy”, typical of the high-end of sophistication of the market economy (see section 4, b), below). In this domain, most of the output to be produced by the parties is reasonably definable *ex ante*.

In the mid-level of complexity of the market economy, there is a diverse mapping of collaborative forms, varying widely according to the features of the relationship involved.⁴⁹ We conclude that this is the realm where, despite this variance, contracting practices are fairly predictable and the formal contract at the heart of the neoclassical view of contract law has significant explanatory traction.

⁴⁹ Delineating a distinction of how the formal and informal in contract law interact in different kinds of relationships (including those involving a high level of sophistication), see Ronald J. Gilson, Charles F. Sabel & Robert E. Scott, *Text and Context: Contract Interpretation as Contract Design*, 100 CORNELL L. REV. 23 (2014).

Generally, in these cases, a formal, written contract will be signed by the parties establishing the terms of their relationship. Often, especially where the relationship is short-term and does not involve many potential unforeseeable contingencies, the formal agreement will be detailed and establish most of the obligations of the parties, creating a suitable reference for their relationship. In these instances, the threat of enforcement in court can serve as an incentive for the parties' voluntary compliance. If not, courts will be able to easily enforce the obligations spelled out in the agreement to solve the conflict through a formalistic approach of contract law – there is a relatively little need to consider contextual elements to solve the disputes involved. In some situations, the parties may themselves calibrate in the terms of the agreement how much of the context should be considered in its interpretation, by combining precise terms with general standards (such as reasonable efforts or good faith) in drafting the contract.⁵⁰

However, other business relationships involve a degree of uncertainty and potentially unforeseeable controversies (especially in long-term relationships), producing an incomplete contract between the parties. In practice, most disputes arising from incomplete contracts are solved between the parties themselves, relationally, incentivized by informal business considerations: moral constraints, the interest in ongoing relationships with the contractual partner and in maintaining a good reputation in the market. Not infrequently, these are reinforced by close personal ties between the actors involved in the business sometimes established over several years.

Whenever these informal incentives are insufficient to guarantee compliance with the agreement or the settlement of controversies between the parties, the default contract law rules will apply. Once again, in this realm, most of the traditional neo-classical contract law rules do, for the most part, apply effectively, with a casual need for minor adjustments. In the mid-level of sophistication of the economy, the contract terms and the contractual performance tend to be reasonably defined, therefore, a court can, with reasonable ease, interpret an agreement in light of commercial considerations and logic of the deal employing the neo-classical contract law rules. Contextual consideration might kick-in, particularly regarding disputes involving long-term incomplete agreements (such as joint ventures), where the parties were unable at the beginning to specify in detail the parties' obligations. In such cases, courts may be more inclined (at least in some jurisdictions) towards implying terms to the 'relational' agreement that reflect the

⁵⁰ Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 3 at 60 et seq.

commercial sense of the business deal.⁵¹ In most situations, however, contextualism will likely be less marked than in the high and low-level of sophistication of the market economy.

Thus, the standard formal contract of neoclassical theory is far from obsolete: in principle, it continues to apply in a large majority of instances of established business practice. However, in a large majority of these cases, it is voluntary compliance in the shadow of the formal agreement that is doing the heavy lifting. The “crowding out” problem is noteworthy in this regard. Indeed, there is something of a formal-informal dichotomy regarding incomplete contracting.⁵² Where the law is to be enforced, relational incentives and trust often fail to develop, except to a minimal degree; where trust/social capital prevail, no formal rules are applied, lest they disrupt the informal relation. This sector of the market economy, overall, corresponds to Weber’s description of the market economy as involving low-level trust (basically, trust in the enforcement of traditional institutions of contract and property) coupled with little discretion between economic agents.⁵³ Therein, the law serves only to enforce contract and property rights, not to maintain relationships. It has long been acknowledged by legal scholarship that, in most circumstances, contracts would be voluntarily complied with, ruling out the need for court enforcement, with the threat of legal coercion at best playing a marginal role in incentivizing compliance. This insight is supported by an overwhelming tranche of empirical studies from a range of different industries and countries.

One of the most authoritative studies on the subject is the seminal one by Macaulay⁵⁴, still considered the foundational sociological study analysing legal enforcement of contracts. It is based on 68 interviews with businesspeople from 43 companies and six law firms in Wisconsin, United States, across a range of different industries and examines how a sample of mid-sized commercial companies would conduct their contractual long-term inter-firm relationships and solve contingencies and disputes arising from their business partnerships.⁵⁵ The results, that revolutionized our understanding of how contracts function, reveal that, in the context of such relationships, legal enforcement has a minimal role. In most situations, parties resolve all

⁵¹ Collins, *supra* note 33.

⁵² Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 38 at 1379–1381.

⁵³ Weber defended the view that the law should be rational and predictable while at the same time guaranteeing a high degree of independence “freed of the bonds of kinship, religion, and other foci of traditional authority and, at the same time, insulated from the arbitrary action of the state”. See D Trubek, *Max Weber on Law and the Rise of Capitalism*, 1972 WIS REV 720, 744 (1972); On a primary source discussing the rational state and rational law, see MAX WEBER, *GENERAL ECONOMIC HISTORY* 338 et seq (1981).

⁵⁴ S Macaulay, *Non-Contractual Relations in Business: A Preliminary Study*, 28 AM. SOCIOLOGICAL REV. 55–67 (1963).

⁵⁵ 17 were machine manufacturers, but none was involved with food products, petroleum, scientific instruments or textiles. See *Id.* at 55–56.

contingencies and disputes informally, with no court intervention: a variety of informal incentives propel the parties not to behave opportunistically, including the need to maintain their reputation in the market, the interest of continued relationships with the other firm(s), business peer-pressure, among others. The role of contract enforcement is restricted to providing the assurance that, in the case of a partial or complete breakdown of the commercial relationship, the law will intervene by applying the contract rules and default contract law norms.

Macauley's results have been confirmed by a range of other such investigations, in a wide variety of regional and industrial settings. In the context of the US, an empirical assessment of 10 chemical and pharmaceutical companies' behavior during shortage periods (in 1974 and 1975), concluded that contract law did not influence how they allocated supply during shortages. According to White, these allocations were undertaken informally between the firms.⁵⁶ A further empirical study involved 84 returned questionnaires sent to United States corporations, of different sizes (most of them with annual sales over a billion dollars), and from different industries (30.5% were conglomerates having diversified businesses).⁵⁷ Once more, the results indicated that the contracts – especially long-term agreements – involved governance mechanisms but were rarely litigated in practice. As reported by Weintraub, the respondents said it was likely that they would consider modifications to the contract requested by the other party, indicating the importance of the business relationship and the reasonableness of the request. Hadfield & Bozovic⁵⁸ published an empirical study of 29 inter-firm business relations in California, US. In the case of commercial contracts in relatively less innovative activities, which involved 12 of the companies in the sample, their results mirrored Macauley's predictions: formal contracts have little relevance for the resolution of arising disputes between long-term contractual partners, and informal relational mechanisms are mainly relied on to solve these disputes.⁵⁹ These non-innovative companies were mostly engaged with the manufacturing of different products (such as candies, brake systems, motorcycle wheels, undergarments), with features that could be easily specified.⁶⁰ Contract planning seems particularly important when relationship-specific investments are observable. Joskow's analysis of a sample of 277 coal contracts supported the hypothesis that, whenever relationship-specific investments are present, longer-term contracts

⁵⁶ JJ White, *Contract Law in Modern Commercial Transactions, an Artifact of Twentieth Century Business Life?*, 22 WASHBURN LAW J. 1 (1982).

⁵⁷ RJ Weintraub, *A Survey of Contract Practice and Policy*, 1992 WIS. LAW REV. 1 (1992).

⁵⁸ G Hadfield & I Bozovic, *Scaffolding: using formal contracts to support informal relations in support of innovation*, 5 WIS. LAW REV. 981 (2016).

⁵⁹ *Id.* at 11 et seq.

⁶⁰ In relation to innovative transactions, however, the authors present a different picture (explored in the next section).

will be concluded, with specified terms and conditions, rejecting the dependence on repeated bargaining.⁶¹ In a subsequent article, Joskow examines the particular structure of the price adjustment provisions in a sample of about 250 coal contracts, indicating the importance of contract planning in these relationships.⁶² Goldberg and Erickson examined ninety long-term contracts for petroleum coke in a period ranging from 1946 to 1973. They found that the contracts contained a number of provisions to protect specific investments and to minimize the risks involved in the contractual collaboration.⁶³ Complex quantity and price provisions are also found by Mulherin in a large sample of long-term contracts in the coal, geothermal, uranium and natural gas industries, from the 1940's and 1950's.⁶⁴ The importance of informal contracting is particularly highlighted by Palay in a survey of 51 informal, unenforceable agreements between rail-freight carriers and shippers, which were identified through field interviews in the US during 1979.⁶⁵ Since the regulatory framework in place in the rail freight contracting was inadequate to provide incentives for certain idiosyncratic investments sought by the parties, such incentives were created through promises advanced in informal contracting.

The same conclusions have been arrived at in the European case. An empirical study assessing 19 engineering manufacturers, mostly in Bristol, England, by Beale & Dugdale presented results widely supporting Macaulay's argument that, in long-term inter-firm relationships, parties mostly solve their conflicts relationally, without relying on contract planning to solve potential contingencies.⁶⁶ A pilot-study conducted in Denmark examined the contracting practices of 3 firms by Blegvad.⁶⁷ The results indicated that, routinely, in cases of discrete transactions, a more traditional contract law approach is followed, with brief contracts with clear obligations – even though litigation is rare in practice. However, for long-term relationships, more robust contract

⁶¹ PL Joskow, *Contract Duration and Relationship-Specific Investments: Empirical Evidence from Coal Markets*, 77 AM. ECON. REV. 168–185 (1987).

⁶² PL Joskow, *Asset Specificity and the Structure of Vertical Relationships: Empirical Evidence Conference Papers to Celebrate the Fiftieth Anniversary of the Nature Of The Firm*, 4 J. LAW ECON. ORGAN. 95–118 (1988).

⁶³ VP Goldberg & JR Erickson, *Quantity and Price Adjustment in Long-Term Contracts: A Case Study of Petroleum Coke*, 30 J. LAW ECON. 369–398 (1987); See also VP Goldberg, *Price Adjustment in Long-Term Contracts Law, Private Governance and Continuing Relationships*, 1985 WIS. LAW REV. 527–544 (1985).

⁶⁴ The “pre-regulatory” era, see JH Mulherin, *Complexity in Long-Term Contracts: An Analysis of Natural Gas Contractual Provisions*, 2 J. LAW ECON. ORGAN. 105–117 (1986).

⁶⁵ TM Palay, *Avoiding Regulatory Constraints: Contracting Safeguards and the Role of Informal Agreements*, 1 J. LAW ECON. ORGAN. 155–175 (1985); See also TM Palay, *Comparative Institutional Economics: The Governance of Rail Freight Contracting*, 13 J. LEG. STUD. 265–287 (1984).

⁶⁶ “The picture which emerges from our research is, as will be seen, broadly similar to that drawn by Macaulay, and many of the general explanations of why contract law may or may not be used are the same as his.” H Beale & T Dugdale, *Contracts between Businessmen: Planning and the Use of Contractual Remedies*, 2 BR. J. LAW SOC. 45–60, 46 (1975).

⁶⁷ BM Blegvad, *Commercial Relations, Contract, and Litigation in Denmark: A Discussion of Macaulay's Theories*, 24 LAW SOC. REV. 397 (1990).

governance is established, and contingencies are solved mostly informally, with formal enforcement remaining as an unlikely outcome for the case of fall-out between the parties. In a study set in Lyon, France of 10 machine-building companies (1985-1986) with regard to their relationships with suppliers, Lorenz found out that the contract was unlikely to be enforced and that trust was an important element in allowing for the cooperation to succeed.⁶⁸ The relational element, however, was facilitated by governance mechanisms and by the design of the agreement.

The same phenomenon seems to be at play in other contexts, including in the case of transition economies. In a survey conducted in Vietnam between 1995-1997, 259 non-state local firms provided information on their contracting practices.⁶⁹ These were all manufacturing companies, from different industries (ranging from footwear, construction, metal products, food, among others). The study concluded that relational contracting prevailed in the inter-firm relationships, especially in the absence of a formal contract law and considering the lack of alternative suppliers at that time in Vietnam. According to McMillan & Woodruff, when the agreements involved long-term partners, companies would be more likely to extend credit to these customers. In a similar scenario, 36 Bulgarian companies in the food industry were interviewed in 1994, shortly after the country transitioned to a market economy.⁷⁰ At this stage, where resort to courts and the reliability of contract law was still uncertain, Koford & Miller argued that companies relied on relational incentives to assure business, mostly contracting with partners with whom they had established relationships.

The initial message conveyed by this trend of empirical studies was that contract planning had limited importance (particularly in long-term agreements) and the role of default legal rules was minimal, considering the sufficiency of relational incentives to solve contingencies. The more recent case studies (such as Weintraub or Lorenz) start to recognize that governance mechanisms inserted in these agreements might represent important elements to create a framework conducive to cooperation and to the development of trust between the parties.

As Gilson, Sabel and Scott recognize, however, in circumstances where there is a thick market (i.e., a significant number of firms considering themselves to be transacting under the same circumstances) and low uncertainty, a contextualizing regime will often develop, normally

⁶⁸ E. Lorenz, *Trust, contract and economic cooperation*, 23 *CAMB. J. ECON.* 301 (1999).

⁶⁹ J McMillan & C Woodruff, *Interfirm Relationships and Informal Credit in Vietnam*, 114 *Q. J. ECON.* 1285 (1999).

⁷⁰ K Koford & JB Miller, *Contract enforcement in the early transition of an unstable economy*, 30 *ECON. SYST.* 1 (2006).

comprising both substantive norms (different from state legislation) and a private adjudicatory system.⁷¹ This seems to be the case vis-à-vis the empirical evidence discussed in the remaining part of this section. As the market is thick, there is an interest and incentive on the part of a significant number of parties to create a regime that will be collectively beneficial to their transactions. As the uncertainty is low, the group is able (through a trade association or by developing informal rules over time to govern a community of firms, for example) to develop norms that will be adequate, in most cases, for the relationships undertaken by parties in a certain context. Even if the norms are updated regularly, there is sufficient stability allowing for predictable rules to govern the parties throughout their relationship.

In the 1990's, a number of empirical studies started to acknowledge the use of institutional mechanisms – other than traditional legal rules – to organize inter-firm cooperation. They represented an advancement in relation to Macaulay's seminal empirical study, which claimed that little, or no, contract planning or any incentive structure was necessary. In these studies, there is the creation of a significant legal framework – other than state-based legislation – to facilitate cooperation.

In fact, the most important benefit of this form of private ordering would be the creation of a framework conducive to cooperation between the parties.⁷² By creating an institution with social relations, “networks of gossip”, information about the members flows easily, allowing bonding between partners and reputational sanctioning in case of default, thereby encouraging the creation of cooperative partnerships.⁷³ In case of breach, this framework would encourage restoring cooperation by making it less costly for the breaching party to continue to cooperate with the other party to demonstrate that it continues to be a trusted partner and to seek to escape reputational loss.⁷⁴

Specifically, with regard to the role of trade association initiatives in incentivizing cooperation, Bernstein's seminal articles describe private orderings in the context of a wide range of industries. In the diamond industry⁷⁵, she analyzed the functioning of the New York Diamond Dealers Club, comprising 2.000 members with different roles in the industry (manufacturers, wholesalers, brokers, sight dealers). The Club is a member of the World Federation of Diamond Bourses, a

⁷¹ Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 3 at 68 et seq.

⁷² L Bernstein, *Private Commercial Law in the Cotton Industry: Creating Cooperation Through Rules, Norms, and Institutions*, 99 MICH. LAW REV. 1724–1790, 1762 (2001).

⁷³ *Id.* at 1764 et seq.

⁷⁴ *Id.* at 1783 et seq.

⁷⁵ L Bernstein, *Opting out of the Legal System: Extralegal Contractual Relations in the Diamond Industry*, 21 J. LEG. STUD. 115 (1992).

wider organization encompassing the world's twenty diamond bourses – all of them with similar trade rules.⁷⁶ In the area of cotton, Bernstein analyzed the different bodies of law created by different industry associations in the US (American Cotton Shippers Association and the American Textile Manufacturers Institute), to which most of the regional shipping associations and regional exchanges in the US are members.⁷⁷ A condition of membership is to submit disputes under this legal framework to a joint arbitral tribunal created by the aforementioned associations. In the grain industry⁷⁸, Bernstein undertook a case study of the National Grain and Feed Association, demonstrating how a private arbitration court is established to resolve disputes in this field. The enforcement of decisions is mostly voluntary, propelled by relational considerations.

In the extended study of the cotton industry (with conclusions that can be, to a certain extent, generalized to other industries where similar conditions prevail), Bernstein argues that the trade associations' rules differ from the Uniform Commercial Code legal approach in two fundamental ways.⁷⁹ First, the trade institutions provide very precise rules, avoiding the use of general standards such as "reasonable" or "good faith", for instance. Second, they provide under-compensatory damages. In most cases, there will be no need to request a state court for mandatory enforcement, given that most parties will voluntarily comply with the awards issued by the arbitral bodies created by these institutions due to the costs of the non-legal sanctions to be imposed in case of default, notably, reputational sanctions.⁸⁰ As the institutions have a larger membership, information about the default of one of the parties easily and swiftly reaches most of the trading community, which might become cautious about dealing with the breaching firm in the future. Furthermore, non-complying parties can be expelled from the associations, through which the bulk of trade is conducted, thereby seriously undermining their profitability.

Similarly, Deakin, Lane & Wilkinson have undertaken extensive empirical research, comparing inter-firm practices in Britain, Italy and Germany, challenging the, then-predominant assumption that contract planning and incentive structures were rarely employed in inter-firm relationships.⁸¹ Their results indicate the importance of institutional factors in developing trust between the parties and in creating a field conducive to cooperation between them through applications of

⁷⁶ *Id.* at 121.

⁷⁷ Bernstein, *supra* note 72.

⁷⁸ L Bernstein, *Merchant Law in a Merchant Court: Rethinking the Code's Search for Immanent Business Norms*, 144 UNIV. PA. LAW REV. 1765 (1996).

⁷⁹ Bernstein, *supra* note 72 at 1732–1733.

⁸⁰ *Id.* at 1737.

⁸¹ S Deakin, C Lane & F Wilkinson, *Contract Law, Trust Relations, and Incentives for Co-operation: A Comparative Study*, in *CONTRACTS, CO-OPERATION AND COMPETITION* 105–139, 122–123 (S Deakin & J Michie eds., 1997).

the good faith principle, trade associations and standard setting organizations.⁸² Their empirical results demonstrated how, in each jurisdiction and sector studied, these elements had a different importance and interactions for the contractual environment. For instance, while in Germany and Italy the concept of good faith is more refined and connected with industry-level regulation to specify this general concept, in Britain, good faith is less important and industry-level standards relatively rare.⁸³

A similar depiction is presented in the context of transnational supply sale of software, where it has been argued that formal contract law has an even a smaller role than usually thought and that relational sanctioning is the way the relationship is regulated.⁸⁴ An empirical study undertook 31 interviews with software experts from Germany, Romania, Bulgaria and India, and 10 follow-up interviews with 10 German software experts. Dietz claims that companies have not been relying on formal enforcement, despite the high risks involved in these transactions, such as delays or non-conformity to quality.⁸⁵ Rather, with the support of self-enforcing contracts (creating monitoring mechanisms and dividing performance into different phases), especially reputational networks⁸⁶, they collect information about the reliability of partner firms and trust in the circulation of information about breaches over the network so as to make reputational sanctions efficient and discourage violation of contractual obligations. In an international setting, according to the author, the limits of formal contract law are enhanced by the fragmentation of national laws and the difficulties of private international law to deal with highly complex commercial relationships.

The creation of private orderings or contextualizing rules to govern specific relationships is not a new phenomenon; indeed, it is an ancient practice. Avner Greif has studied historical records concerning commercial relationships between Maghribi traders in the Mediterranean in the 11th century and their agents dispersed throughout the world.⁸⁷ He claims that contracts concluded were incomplete and no legal sanctions were employed to counteract potential opportunism in these transactions. Instead, the Maghribi developed a private order through trade coalitions.

⁸² *Id.* at 111 et seq.

⁸³ *Id.* at 112–113.. See also the description of the German productive system and the importance of good faith as opposed to Britain, G Teubner, *Legal Irritants: Good Faith in British Law or How Unifying Law Ends up in New Divergences*, 61 MOD. LAW REV. 11–32, 25–26 (1998).

⁸⁴ THOMAS DIETZ, GLOBAL ORDER BEYOND LAW: HOW INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES FACILITATE RELATIONAL CONTRACTING IN INTERNATIONAL TRADE 58 et seq (2014).

⁸⁵ *Id.* at 166.

⁸⁶ *Id.* at 167 et seq.

⁸⁷ A Greif, *The Maghribi traders: a reappraisal?*, 65 ECON. HIST. REV. 445–469 (2012); A Greif, *Contract Enforceability and Economic Institutions in Early Trade: The Maghribi Traders' Coalition*, 83 AM. ECON. REV. 525–548 (1993); A Greif, *Reputation and Coalitions in Medieval Trade: Evidence on the Maghribi Traders*, 49 J. ECON. HIST. 857–882 (1989).

Through these institutions, information about agents' conduct would flow among the Maghribi and collective punishment would be secured, both through the threat of not being hired in the future and reputational damage that could undermine the agents' activities overall. In the absence of contractual provisions, the merchant law (customary law) would apply to these relationships. A similar picture is presented by Milstron & Weingast regarding commerce between merchants in the Champagne fairs in the 12th and 13th century.⁸⁸

In sum, the mid-level of sophistication of the market economy is the stronghold of formalist, neo-classical Contract law, where, by and large, it is accepted that the agreement should be enforced according to its own terms, with the law giving consideration to the context in exceptional circumstances. Given the relatively lower levels of uncertainty involved in these relationships, the parties might be able to create, in many cases, contracts sufficient to regulate their activities. Whenever they cannot (as in long-term incomplete agreements), the uncertainty will be minimal enough for the parties to solve disputes among themselves relationally, due to the aforementioned business incentives. Contract law will be seldom enforced in courts, for the parties will mostly solve their contingencies informally. Contracting planning is either unimportant in less complex transactions or, in some more complex transactions, might increasingly require governance mechanisms. In instances involving a significant number of economic agents considering themselves to be transacting under the same circumstances, often contextualizing regimes will be generated, potentially involving both special rules and a specialized adjudicatory body. Here, the rules generated tend to have a more formalistic perspective, instead of implying terms based on contextual considerations (such as course of dealing, course of performance or trade usages), giving the parties greater latitude to determine the mix of legal and extra-legal arrangements that will frame their relationship. While this is the overall picture, there may be exceptions, for instance, judgments involving so-called relational contracts, such as long-term joint venture agreements, where courts in some jurisdictions may find more leeway to imply terms into the agreement.⁸⁹

⁸⁸ PR Milgrom & BR Weingast, *The role of institutions in the revival of trade: the law merchant, private judges, and the Champagne fairs*, 2 *ECON. POLIT.* 1–23 (1990). See also A Greif, P Milgrom & BR Weingast, *Coordination, Commitment, and Enforcement: The Case of the Merchant Guild*, 102 *J. POLIT. ECON.* 745–776 (1994).

⁸⁹ Collins, *supra* note 33.

b. High level of sophistication of the market economy

At the upper end of sophistication of the market economy (the “knowledge economy”) are located the most advanced practices of production, accessible only to a small share of the work force.⁹⁰ Firms typical of the so-called knowledge or experimental economy⁹¹ are typically simultaneously dispersed throughout the world yet connected to each other⁹², production has been rearranged to become a practice of constant learning. Faster innovation cycles have rendered higher knowledge and technology unable to sustain competitive advantages over extended periods of time: the ability to learn, to experiment, to innovate constantly, rapidly and reliably has become the central value in the production of advanced innovation in these vanguards.⁹³ The emblematic example is the Toyota method of production, which established a production process for the rapid detection of defects, with specialization in the problem-solving abilities to deal with the identified issues and to improve them.⁹⁴ In the past, the process of mass production in factories was the rule, with an inventory of replacements for inputs or machines to substitute them once defects were encountered as a way to assuring the uninterrupted functioning of the process of production. Nowadays, it is increasingly common for companies to adopt the strategy of stopping the process of production once problems are detected, identifying the bottlenecks, and investing heavily in problem-solving capabilities to solve them as quickly as possible. This procedure has, in many cases, led to better and cheaper production processes and outputs. Moreover, the ‘Toyota system of production’ has led to increases in productivity and innovation. Paradigmatic examples of projects undertaken in the domain of the knowledge economy involve the co-creation of innovative models of aerospace, new chemical components, drones customized for precision agriculture, apps for smartphones and other such cutting-edge ventures.

In this sector, contracting practices present a different picture from the one presented in the previous section. Typically, these practices involve a high degree of uncertainty, requiring sophisticated forms of governance, different from that observable in the mid-level of

⁹⁰ RM UNGER, *THE KNOWLEDGE ECONOMY* (2019).

⁹¹ Examining the contrasting culture and productive practices in two different regions, one more representative of the collaborative knowledge economy (Silicon Valley) and the other of more vertical and competitive traditional production practices (Route 128), see AL SAXENIAN, *REGIONAL ADVANTAGE: CULTURE AND COMPETITION IN SILICON VALLEY AND ROUTE 128* (1996).

⁹² On the dispersion of productive vanguards throughout the world, often connected to each other (through ‘brain circulation’), see AL SAXENIAN, *THE NEW ARGONAUTS: REGIONAL ADVANTAGE IN A GLOBAL ECONOMY* (2007).

⁹³ C Sabel & M Dorf, *A constitution of democratic experimentalism*, 98 *COLUMBIA LAW REV.* 267–292, 292 ff. (1998).

⁹⁴ STEVEN J. SPEAR, *CHASING THE RABBIT: HOW MARKET LEADERS OUTDISTANCE THE COMPETITION AND HOW GREAT COMPANIES CAN CATCH UP AND WIN*, FOREWORD BY CLAY CHRISTENSEN 159–162; 193 ff (1 edition ed. 2008).

sophistication of the market economy. In the present sphere, there is a need for a *continuous, dialogic, joint process of decision making between the parties to specify uncertainty*. In an innovative project, both the insiders (or practitioners) in the market, as well as the outsiders (e.g., regulators or generalist judges) are unable to predict what will be the better approach to deal with a certain problem.⁹⁵ There is a need for a framework allowing for the constant remolding of their duties and rights, creating a joint procedure to respond to uncertainty involving the parties.

The relational incentives that were efficient in the mid-level are no longer sufficient alone to solve contingencies, for the level of uncertainty risks creating misunderstanding between the parties: they cannot clearly distinguish whether the action of another party represents a defection or a legitimate action with the purpose of generating innovation (the “observability problem”).⁹⁶ This undermines the efficiency of the monitoring of the counterparty. Furthermore, the relational mechanism, based upon the threat of punishment to the breaching party (through reputational shaming in the market), would also likely discourage risky, experimentalist action that would be necessary to generate innovation.

As a result, the picture emerging is as follows. Since there is pervasive uncertainty as to whether or how a highly innovative output is to be produced and its final features, the contract cannot specify several of the parties’ obligations in the contract. The contracts for innovation are then structured as incomplete agreements, but with governance mechanisms creating a procedure for the continuous specification of performance characteristics.⁹⁷ For instance, while the parties establish their general aim to produce a certain output, they may not be able to specify what production process will be followed, since there is no previous precedent to be used as a model to generate a highly innovative output. Rather, they may establish joint committees formed by the members of the different firms to make decisions as to how this process will be conducted as their cooperation evolves. Furthermore, contingencies involving agreements are solved informally, through escalated dispute resolution mechanisms established by the contracts. The degree of enforcement required for these agreements is still uncertain (as few cases have been litigated/arbitrated), but the understanding advanced by braiding theory is that “low-powered enforcement” should be allowed.⁹⁸ In other words, the enforcement of the agreements through specific performance or expectation damages (forcing the cooperation to move forward) should

⁹⁵ RJ Gilson, C Sabel & RE Scott, *Contract and Innovation: The Limited Role of Generalist Courts in the Evolution of Novel Contractual Terms*, 88 NYU LAW REV. 170–174, 210 (2012).

⁹⁶ Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 38 at 1392.

⁹⁷ R Gilson, C Sabel & R Scott, *Contracting for Innovation: Vertical Disintegration and Interfirm Collaboration*, 109 COLUMBIA LAW REV. 431–502, 472 (2009).

⁹⁸ Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 38 at 1415 et seq.

not be allowed, for that would discourage experimental, innovative projects that require flexibility for the parties to, amicably, go their separate ways in case the evolution of the collaboration does not live up to its initial promise. However, whenever the duties of cooperation are not duly fulfilled, reliance damages should be collected as a means to protect the parties' preliminary investments. One of the most notable recent developments in US Law, indeed, regards the enforceability of a duty to negotiate in good faith agreements to collaborate:

Recently, however, in a major shift in doctrine, courts have relaxed the common law rule under which parties are either fully bound or not bound at all. Instead, a new enforcement rule is emerging to govern cases where the parties contemplate further negotiations. (...) The shift comes from courts now recognizing that welfare gains can result from attaching some level of formal enforcement to agreements to collaborate that were intended to bind despite the need for further negotiation. The new default rule thus enforces "a mutual commitment to negotiate together in good faith in an effort to reach final agreement."⁹⁹

This emergent rule, creating the possibility of low-powered enforcement for agreements to collaborate, is still fundamentally legally uncertain. Nonetheless, it is clear that there will be a greater level of contextualism involved in analysing the enforceability of these agreements by courts than that present in most cases in the mid-level of the economy.

The empirical analysis of legal agreements involving inter-firm collaborative innovation has been more extensive in the US than in other jurisdictions. The seminal work is Gilson et al's series of articles on contracting for innovation, examining the different mechanisms used by private parties to deal with the challenges of uncertainty and coordination in these relationships.¹⁰⁰

Analyzing ten prototypical contracts from a number of different industries in their series of articles, Gilson et al claim that these agreements share three features¹⁰¹: transactions involving projects which one single firm cannot undertake alone, thus requiring strategic alliances with other companies; a high degree of uncertainty in the development of a new product or a distinct production process that has never been pursued before and whose risk cannot be estimated

⁹⁹ *Id.* at 1426.

¹⁰⁰ Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 97; Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 38; Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 95.

¹⁰¹ Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 97 at 451.

probabilistically; an iterative process of collaboration between companies to exchange information and know-how and to continuously adjust the terms of the cooperation between the parties, since they cannot establish *ex ante* their relationship's terms due to the uncertainty involved.

In practice, Gilson et al claim this cooperation is structured mostly through sophisticated governance mechanisms. Perusing a few paradigmatic contracts for innovation, they argue that the most common mechanisms are 1) establishment of duties of cooperation and exchange of information for the parties to check their compatibility with each other and initiate collaboration, which, however, do not force the continuation of their relationship; 2) the establishment of escalated dispute-resolution mechanisms, with involvement of steering committees and senior top managers of all companies in the project.

For Gilson et al, these contracts braid formal and informal contracting. This braiding is mostly achieved by establishing *formal* agreements that create a contractual landscape suitable for the development of informal incentives for the parties to collaborate (i.e., trust, business considerations). The contracts for innovation contain a few formal rules that impose upon the parties the participation in processes of cooperation that make the behavior of each party more observable.¹⁰² These processes or “contractual milestones” are moments where the parties must come together to cooperate, check their compatibility and then decide whether to continue cooperating or not. The contracts will not impose the continuation of the cooperation, but as the parties voluntarily keep on cooperating, the costs of switching partners will become higher.¹⁰³ As the parties have voluntarily continued cooperating, they invested in each other, acquired know-how and expertise related to the other company and developed communication channels. To forego these advantages would incur significant costs for the companies, especially when compatible partners with expertise might be lacking in the market. The informal side, therefore, gradually creeps in, and serves as a mechanism to undermine opportunism where formal legal sanctions are no longer available. In the case of defection in the initial phases of experimental cooperation (in the “contractual milestones”), Gilson et al argue that formal legal enforcement should be restricted to “low-powered enforcement”, i.e., to the restitution of the incurred costs.¹⁰⁴

¹⁰² See the detailed explanation of the theory in *Id.* at 473 et seq.

¹⁰³ *Id.* at 481 et seq.

¹⁰⁴ Gilson, Sabel, and Scott, *supra* note 38 at 1415 et seq.

Gilson et. al's characterization is supported by a number of other studies. Hadfield & Bozovic¹⁰⁵ find that 17 companies undertaking innovative transactions display markedly different contracting practices relative to the 12 companies they looked at that were classified as non-innovative.¹⁰⁶ Parties heavily relied on contract planning (demonstrated by the significant amount of time and effort employed in drafting agreements), using their agreements as guiding plans, revising them when necessary, but still relying on enforcement through informal mechanisms. According to Hadfield & Bozovic, in most cases, compliance and punishment will be undertaken through relational incentives.¹⁰⁷

A more recent survey of a group of 146 "alliance-contracts" to innovate, from a wide range of industries (life science, semiconductor, software and chemical industries) by Jennejohn¹⁰⁸ identified recurrent patterns and sought to explain the reasons for variations. The access to these forms of contracts in the United States is facilitated as several of them are publicly available through the US Securities Exchange Commission (hereinafter, "SEC").¹⁰⁹ Jennejohn endorses some of the core claims of braiding theory, defending the finding that formal and informal complement each other in innovative transactions. Nonetheless, he indicates gaps and limitations in the theory, intending to develop it rather than reject it.¹¹⁰ His main assertion is that braiding theory focuses excessively on opportunism between the partners as a cause for the design of contract governance, neglecting other hazards in the collaborative context, which are important to understand the variety in contractual design.¹¹¹ Based on his empirical assessment, he claims that a better explanation requires a consideration of a wider number of factors other than opportunism, proposing a theory of 'multi-valent contracting'. According to him, the main factors to be added are spillovers and entropy, elements typical of collaborative relationships. Spillovers refer to the difficulty of defining ex ante the value of assets (especially intellectual property (IP) rights) that may emerge as an outcome of the contractual collaboration.¹¹² The parties need to spend resources on establishing the concept of these assets and on policing their boundaries. If

¹⁰⁵ Hadfield and Bozovic, *supra* note 58.

¹⁰⁶ "They included the relationship between a biotech start up and a pharmaceutical manufacturer involved in the execution of a milestone acquisition agreement, a collaboration between an online platform connecting users with expert knowledge and a firm that provides identity-verification services, and a joint-product development agreement between a specialized circuit manufacturer and a software developer." *Id.* at 15.

¹⁰⁷ *Id.* at 7.

¹⁰⁸ M Jennejohn, *The Private Order of Innovation Networks*, 68 *STANFORD LAW REV.* 281 (2016).

¹⁰⁹ Criteria for disclosure of these agreements is in the US Code of Federal Regulation §229.601(b)(10) on "Material Contracts". Online access online is available through the EDGAR Search Tools at the Securities Exchange Commission website, see <http://www.sec.gov/edgar/searchedgar>.

¹¹⁰ Jennejohn, *supra* note 108 at 291.

¹¹¹ *Id.* at 293.

¹¹² *Id.* at 314, 316.

a new technological process has been developed in a rapidly developing field, such as the software industry or the semiconductor industry, it becomes necessary to spend resources on identifying that specific technology's value, labelling it, and policing its use, lest it may be traded deceitfully by one of the partners in the collaborative venture. The other relevant factor is entropy, i.e. the costs to 'synchronize efforts and learning processes among team members'.¹¹³ In complex projects, the parties must spend resources on communicating adequately and effectively to achieve a functional final product.

Baquero conducted an in-depth study of 11 Brazilian companies that concluded inter-firm collaborations—in the context of a variety of industries, ranging from chemical to biochemical to agribusiness—to co-create advanced innovation, both with other domestic and/or foreign firms.¹¹⁴ His results indicate the consistent use of an (adaptable and variable) array of governance mechanisms that parties build into their agreements to constantly specify uncertainty, such as steering committees constituted by members of the different firms, the breakdown of productive effort into discrete milestones, escalated dispute resolution mechanisms and financial rewards for the achievement of uncertain objectives in the context of the project. Indeed, contractual governance seems to be the main instrument to address problems of internal coordination between members in a collaborative network of contracts for innovation, as reinforced by the few disputes arriving at courts and arbitral tribunals. Some particularities were observed, perhaps connected to the circumstances for the incubation of innovation in a developing country. The first distinction, identified by several interviewees, refers to the customary participation of research institutes or universities in these projects. Although in developed countries collaboration with such entities is recurrent, in the case of Brazil most scientific expertise resides in universities and research institutes, with a small proportion employed in the private sector.¹¹⁵ The implication is that several of these collaborations may be subject to the specific administrative legislation/regulation involving requisites for contracting with public entities, affecting many contracts for innovation.¹¹⁶ A second distinction relates to the fact that, often, in the research

¹¹³ *Id.* at 314.

¹¹⁴ PM BAQUERO, NETWORKS OF COLLABORATIVE CONTRACTS FOR INNOVATION (forthcoming).

¹¹⁵ 67,5% of the researchers in Brazil are employed in higher learning institutions, while a meager 26,2% are employed in companies – a level way below countries such as the US, Germany and Japan. Brazil - Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, *Estratégia Nacional de Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação 2012-2015 – Balanço das Atividades Estruturantes 2011* 41-42 (2012).

¹¹⁶ An example of that, in the Brazilian context, is the previous version of Article 9 of the Innovation Law (Law 10.973/2004). Art. 9 formerly established that, in collaborative relationships involving a public Institute for Science and Technology (such as a public university or a public company involved in research activities), the public entity will necessarily retain the IP rights commensurate with the proportion of its investments. The result was that many collaborations were discouraged where a commercial firm (often carrying the full costs of developing and commercializing a certain product, based on the collaboratively

phase), contractual collaborations to develop innovation in Brazil are “pre-competitive” ventures, that is, projects undertaken by several companies to solve a common technological problem common to that industry. Once a solution is found, each company then moves on to produce their own product independently. That undermines the risks of coordination of the relationship among the parties as they will not be exposed to the risks of co-developing and jointly commercialising products; rather, each will have its own separate product, although they may have used a common technology to develop it separately. This means less need to establish governance mechanisms to coordinate the relationship, but, at the same time, less possibilities in the development of innovation. A third distinction refers to the few existing cases of contractual co-creation to produce advanced innovation involving small and medium companies in the Brazilian context, which are often cautious about sharing information and technology with larger companies, lest they have their ideas stolen. This conundrum indicates the need to devise institutional alternatives to facilitate projects of co-creation between small and medium companies and larger companies, such as the creation of consortia that could represent and provide different kinds of assistance to the smaller firms.

Furthermore, empirical evidence on “braided” contracts have been found in instances ranging from the Chinese smartphone industry to Hollywood. In China, one case study was conducted on the strategic alliance between companies in the smartphone industry.¹¹⁷ The findings in this instance generally supported braiding theory but proposed a few differences in the context of an emerging economy. The case study claimed that mutual trust was a crucial condition for contracting for innovation to flourish; without it, traditional formal contracts would be concluded, instead of braided agreements. The study further rejected the idea that the parties had an informal agreement to constrain opportunistic renegotiations in this setting. Rather, they found the agreement contained flexible exit rules and iterative informal contracting that would provide stability for the transaction in this uncertain setting. “Braided” contractual practices have also been noted in the Hollywood film industry, particularly in agreement between studios and other production entities and high-value talent, the movie stars.¹¹⁸ This is a setting involving high

created technology) would have no incentives to make the needed investments, as its rate of profits from the IP royalties would not be sufficient to cover the project costs. Moreover, the public entities, most often, would not have the financial resources and organizational abilities to develop and commercialize the product alone. As a result, experimentalism and innovation would be hindered. Article 9 was rightly revised in 2016, and now establishes that public ICTs shall be able to transfer to the private partner firm the entire IP rights in exchange for a financial or non-financial commensurate compensation. This is not to suggest that this is the best solution in all cases, but the point is that this possibility should not be ruled out by the legislation. See Art. 9, § 3º of the Innovation Law (Law 10.973/2004).

¹¹⁷ H Zhang, J Wen & J Wu, *Contracting for innovation: the difference in a case with fast-changing industrial background in China*, 21 J. GLOB. INF. TECHNOL. MANAG. 5, 20–21 (2018).

¹¹⁸ J Barnett, *Hollywood Deals: Soft Contracts for Hard Markets*, 64 DUKE LAW J. 605, 609–610 (2015).

uncertainty, where the participation of the movie star, the potential of acquiring the required finance, the chances of success of the movie are generating a constant uncertainty regarding the parties commitment to the project. In this context, evidence has indicated that parties often tread an intermediate path between formal and informal contracting. They rather adopt a form of ‘soft’ contracting, where they base their relationship upon both some formal elements (memoranda, draft contracts, e-mails), which may be legally enforceable in certain conditions, but not always, and combine them with the reputational incentives that arise in the context of the movie industry. Besides these case studies, a series of legal studies have analyzed the potential governance mechanisms (potentially applicable to coordinate these complex transactions), examining the creation and functions of steering committees (or contractual boards) in strategic alliances¹¹⁹, financial incentives¹²⁰, non-compete clauses’ role in producing innovation¹²¹, the use of advanced technology to foster coordination and collaboration between contractual partners¹²², the use of outsourcing relationships to develop specific forms of governance¹²³ and the aforementioned blending of formal and informal law (braiding) in designing collaborative relationships.¹²⁴ In the biotechnology and semiconductor industry, Klausner discusses two case studies on strategic alliances examining the governance mechanisms employed, namely, structural financial payments, limitations of competition, and procedures for exchange of information, coordination and decision-making.¹²⁵

In sum, the governance of these relationships is undertaken through contracts containing a differentiated governance framework for the continuous specification of uncertainty and controversies are solved internally, mostly through an escalated dispute resolution procedure. For braiding theory, exceptionally, low-powered enforcement could take place, with courts awarding reliance damages for violation of cooperation duties. This form of enforcement of cooperation duties would require a certain degree of “institutional” contextualism to analyze

¹¹⁹ DG Smith, *The Exit Structure of Strategic Alliances Symposium: Uncorporation: A New Age*, UNIV. ILL. LAW REV. 303 (2005).

¹²⁰ GW Dent, *Lawyers and Trust in Business Alliances*, 58 BUS. LAWYER 45–82 (2002) (notably, mentioning “staged” financing).

¹²¹ *Id.* at 53.

¹²² CJ Circo, *A Case Study in Collaborative Technology and the Intentionally Relational Contract: Building Information Modeling and Construction Industry Contracts*, 67 ARK. LAW REV. 873 (2014) (discussing the use of the Building Information Modelling – BIM – as a technology facilitating collaboration between partners in the construction industry).

¹²³ G Geis, *The Space Between Markets and Hierarchies*, 95 VA. LAW REV. 95–132 (2009); see also G Geis, *An Empirical Examination of Business Outsourcing Transactions*, 96 VA. LAW REV. 241 (2009).

¹²⁴ M Jennejohn, *Contract Adjudication in a Collaborative Economy*, 5 VA. LAW BUS. REV. 173–237, 117 et seq (2010).

¹²⁵ M Klausner, *Governance mechanism in long-term contract*, in CONTRACT GOVERNANCE: DIMENSIONS IN LAW AND INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH 218–233, 231–232 (S Grundmann, F Möslin, & K Riesenhuber eds., 2015).

whether a violation has occurred, making use of the information collected through the cooperation procedures established by the parties in their agreement.

As in the mid-level of sophistication, in the high-end of the market economy, once the market is thick, there is greater potential for a collective action response by a multitude of actors. In this case, their objective is not simply to maximize their common gains, but to undermine the potential risks created in a highly uncertain market by a significant number of actors acting simultaneously, where the damages created by one actor might affect the whole industry (and potentially outsiders as well). To prevent that, instead of relying only on bilateral contracts, either private, public or mixed ordering frameworks are developed.

These orderings, however, are distinct from the ones referred to in the section on the mid-level of sophistication of the market economy. Instead, they have a special design to allow for collaborative relationships with the need for continuous adjustments. In the private orderings on the cotton, grain or diamond industry, studied by Bernstein, for example, there is a significant level of stability and the output is sufficiently defined to discard the need for the continuous and collaborative revision of the parties' obligation as the parties evolve in the project. While there might be regular updates in the legal rules provided by trade institutions, these will not be as dynamic and continuous as in the cases involving collaborative innovation, neither will it necessarily require the parties' input of information for reshaping the rules.

Legal scholarship has now developed a taxonomy for contextualizing regimes established by trade associations and leaders of supply chains to deal with high levels of uncertainty. They are often referred to as "experimentalist regimes". Experimentalist architectures share four main features.¹²⁶ First, general framework goals established by a central body (the leading company in a network chain, an appointed management body, a regulatory/certification agency), often created through a participatory process involving the regulated entities. Second, discretion for lower level entities (e.g., the firm in a supply chain) to pursue these general goals as they deem reasonable in the local context. Third, monitoring and evaluating the performance of different local units, based on agreed methodologies and benchmarks, with experiences of success being shared between the parties. Fourth, the framework goals and the contextual practices are revised by the parties themselves in light of the accumulated knowledge resulting from this experimentalist practice. This crucial step involves a dialogic process between them, where they

¹²⁶ C Sabel & J Zeitlin, *Learning from Difference: The New Architecture of Experimentalist Governance in the EU*, in EXPERIMENTALIST GOVERNANCE IN THE EUROPEAN UNION: TOWARDS A NEW ARCHITECTURE 1, 3 (C Sabel & J Zeitlin eds., 2010).

seek to learn from other entities and to improve their own process. Distinct institutional arrangements might be established to pursue this experimentalism.¹²⁷

The Toyota Production System is a reference point as an experimentalist regime, where, as Simon notes, the different companies involved in the chain start producing something and continuously provide information to an organizing body about the perceived risks of a certain activity, establish a benchmark of issues to constantly monitor, measure failures and problems, and establish mechanisms for the correction of these issues.¹²⁸ There is no *a priori* definitive regulatory benchmark, however. The regulatory standard is being constantly updated and reassessed based on previously established procedures for regularly measuring and correcting risks. According to Herrigel, formalized “experimentalist” corporate production systems have diffused widely among multinationals:

“CPSs have diffused widely among manufacturing MNCs. Many companies brand their CPS (e.g. The Siemens Production System or “The Volkswagen Way”). The companies also characteristically provide their own corporate names to the mechanisms of goal setting, self-evaluation (performance review), benchmarking, joint problem solving and goal revision. Despite this nominal variety, however, all follow the general experimentalist logic (...).”¹²⁹

A slightly different approach on the structuring of collaborative innovation between multiple parties is suggested in the context of procurement contracts in the US.¹³⁰ In relationships between different OEMs (Original Equipment Manufacturer – a company that creates a subsystem to be incorporated in another company’s final product) and its suppliers, it is argued, the contracts are very vague and meant not to be enforced, but to create a relational framework inducing cooperation. Some of the leading companies establishing this framework, analyzed in the case study by Bernstein, are John Deere, Caterpillar, Navistar and Harley.¹³¹

For Bernstein, however, contract governance mechanisms will be less efficient in the innovation-related transactions where there is pervading uncertainty.¹³² There, the potential to assess the

¹²⁷ *Id.* at 3.

¹²⁸ On experimentalism in the Toyota production system, see W Simon, *Toyota Jurisprudence: Legal Theory and Rolling Rule Regimes*, in *LAW AND NEW GOVERNANCE IN THE EU AND THE US* 11–40 (G De Búrca & J Scott eds., 2006).

¹²⁹ G Herrigel, *Experimentalist systems in manufacturing multinationals: German automobile and machinery examples*, 14 *CRIT. PERSPECT. INT. BUS.* 362–382 (2018).

¹³⁰ L Bernstein, *Beyond relational contracts: social capital and network governance in procurement contracts*, 7 *J. LEG. ANAL.* 561–621 (2015).

¹³¹ *Id.* at 578–579.

¹³² *Id.* at 578–579.

partners' performance is low and there is greater room for misunderstanding. In those contexts, governance mechanisms would foster social capital between the firms through the exchange of information, through the personal ties created between their employees, through the experience of jointly facing and solving problems, by reciprocal specific investments and by the observation of norms of reciprocal flexibility.¹³³ In this context, social capital is not an immediate outcome of the contracts, but a gradual process that might take years to develop.¹³⁴

Bernstein argues that "structural social capital"¹³⁵ can be efficiently designed when there is no possibility of waiting for the gradual development of social capital. This structured social capital refers to the position of firms in relation to their contracting partners within a network of firms. By looking at two examples (biotech alliances and OEM's), she proposes that the more *central* the companies are in a network (i.e., the more the companies have links to other firms in a network and the more their partners have the same links) and the more *proximate* they are (i.e., the less the number of intermediates between two firms), the greater will be the structural social capital between them. Due to their proximity, more information will be available, and it will be easier to sanction each other in case of misbehavior. Similarly, the central firms in a network have more connections and information about their partners and information about their own misbehavior travels faster. Thus, parties are incentivized to act less opportunistically.

Cafaggi presents a more nuanced view, with examples of "responsive regulation", illustrating that, in certain industries, monitoring is performed with the collaboration of third-party certifiers, having some enforcement power over the regulated companies.¹³⁶ The certifiers signal "the existence of risks or spotting mistakes that can be corrected through cooperative practices".¹³⁷ There is evidence of companies' codes of conduct gradually requiring suppliers' compliance with additional certification requirements as they advance their cooperation in the chain.¹³⁸ In specific scenarios, contracts contain references to external regulatory standards or certification schemes then incorporated into the agreement.¹³⁹ Cafaggi provides evidence illustrating where this form

¹³³ *Id.* at 592 et seq.

¹³⁴ *Id.* at fn 96.

¹³⁵ *Id.* at 599.

¹³⁶ F Cafaggi, *Private regulation and industrial organization: contractual governance and the network approach*, in *CONTRACT GOVERNANCE - DIMENSIONS IN LAW AND INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* 343–376, 358 (2015) see also fns 51-52.

¹³⁷ *Id.* at 358.

¹³⁸ Cafaggi mentions the UTZ Core Code of Conduct Version 1.0 for Group and Multi-group Certification – where, for different kinds of commodities, four block monitoring control points are established for compliance with regulations, but only two of them are initially mandatory, with the others becoming obligatory in subsequent years of the cooperation. *Id.* at fn 53.

¹³⁹ F Cafaggi, *The Regulatory Functions of Transnational Commercial Contracts: New Architectures*, 36 *FORDHAM INT. LAW J.* 1557–1618, 1558–1560 and accompanying footnotes (2013).

of incorporation has occurred, for instance, in contracts referencing transnational regulations in food safety¹⁴⁰ or to do with the incorporation of environmental transnational regulations in commercial agreements.¹⁴¹

In sum, in the high-end of sophistication of the market economy, contracting practices with high uncertainty prevail, requiring complex governance mechanisms that allow for the constant specification of uncertainty in incomplete agreements. Contract planning, therefore, is much more significant than in the mid-level of sophistication of the market economy. In practice, adjudication is unlikely, for most contingencies are solved based on relational incentives and through the dispute resolution mechanisms established. In some cases, however, it is acknowledged that some form of enforcement is required (e.g., “low-powered enforcement”, granting reliance damages to compensate for the violation of cooperation duties). This form of enforcement requires a certain degree of “institutional” contextualism in analysing agreements. When a number of parties is involved in a co-creation project, they will often create forms of experimentalist or responsive regulation regimes to govern their relationship, also allowing for the constant learning and revision of their obligations. Often, compliance with these regulations will be voluntary, but there is empirical indication that, in some cases, special forms of enforcement mechanisms might be present (e.g., through third-party certifiers right to request performance lest the parties might be excluded from the certification process).

c. **Low-level of sophistication of the market economy**

The lower end of sophistication in the market economy is, perhaps, the most heterogenous of the three categories. This segment of the economy comprises, simultaneously, situations governed by fairly settled legal, or even convention-based, equilibria as well as more novel cases involving a high degree of uncertainty, thereby requiring different forms of governance and variations of contract law.

¹⁴⁰ Amended and Restated Manufacturing Agreement, GFA Brands, Inc.- Ventura Foods (...) (“Ventura shall provide Customer with the following policies, which shall be updated and resubmitted to Customer from time to time: Allergen Policy, HACCP Plan and Metal Detection Policy.”); Amended and Restated Master Distribution Agreement, Aramark SCM, Inc. para. A(1) (2006) (...) (“All Suppliers must establish and administer the following programs: 1. An operating Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point Program. . . .”). *Id.* at fn 6. These are food regulations issued by the FAO, available at <http://www.fao.org/docrep/w8088e/w8088e00.HTM>.

¹⁴¹ “License Agreement, Motorola, Inc.-Forward Indus., (...) Para. 3(a) (“Manufacturer will implement a functioning environmental management system in accordance with ISO 14001 or equivalent”); *id.* para. 3(b) (“Manufacturer certifies that Products and their parts do not contain and are not manufactured with a process that uses any Class I ozone-depleting substances”).” *Id.* at 352, fns 6 and 7.

This section seeks to delineate the main contracting patterns identifiable in the low level of sophistication of the market economy. At the outset, we describe the familiar types of transactions that would be expected in this sector, which involve a low degree of uncertainty, i.e., relationships between private parties with similar technical knowledge and consumer law cases. These situations predictably involve little financial value, negligible capital, primitive knowledge/technology and no need for sophisticated governance mechanisms. After briefly describing these predictable patterns, however, we move on to identify a set of contracting practices in the low level of sophistication of the market economy that may involve a high degree of uncertainty and present a completely different picture, one which resembles, in some aspects, the high level of sophistication of the market economy.

Indeed, many of the transactions in this realm may be considered legally, and contractually, trivial. The first identifiable pattern of transactions is dominated by relationships between private parties (either firms or individuals) with similar technical knowledge (as opposed to consumer law cases), often undertaken through bilateral contracts involving clearly defined performance (e.g., delivery of certain goods or services) and generally modest financial value. Typical instances include sales of goods contracts, services contracts, rental agreements and other private agreements required for the functioning of firms and for private parties' basic business activities. They do not, for the most part, involve transactions to do with production/distribution in the market (at least not on a large scale), but rather basic supplies for use. In these kinds of transactions, often there is no obstacle to exchange contracts defining clearly the required duties and obligations of the parties. The degree of contextualism required to regulate these relationships might vary case-by-case, according to the jurisdiction, and to the potential risks involved in each situation. Overall, however, there is nothing preventing a clear contractual allocation of risk between the parties. Once again, different legal systems might have different views on the balance between contextualism and formalism in these contracts (giving greater latitude to freedom of contract or to good faith principles). However, it seems that the ability to contractually specify the parties' obligations is significant in these relationships – therefore, the tendency is to have a more formalist contractual perspective applied to them.

The second identifiable pattern involves contracting practices that fall within consumer law, due to the asymmetry of information and technical knowledge in the relationship between the parties. In this domain, which we do not intend to examine at length, usually a more protective interpretation towards the consumer will prevail, especially whenever standard contract terms are inserted into these agreements. Duties of good faith, disclosure, transparency, among others,

are markedly strong in these relationships. Therefore, a formalist interpretation, in this instance, tends to give way to a more contextualist interpretation.

There are a relatively few empirical studies regarding consumer contracting practices and what exists does not paint a clear-cut picture. For instance, Ross & Littlefield examined customer complaints against a major mass retailer in Denver, Colorado, US (one of the largest sellers of TV sets and home appliances in the area), finding that the customers usually received concessions more generous than legally required.¹⁴² This behaviour was motivated by the retailer's belief that, for long-run commercial interest, it was better to deal generously with customers. As a result, court adjudication was minimized in this context. In other countries, such as Brazil, we observe a marked rise in the number of consumer claims examined by courts in the past few years.¹⁴³ This indicates a low percentage of voluntary compliance with consumer law rules, with consumers seeking judicial assistance to enforce their rights. In other words, informal incentives were insufficient in these kinds of situation to guarantee the resolution of contingencies and disputes in such relationships; rather, courts had to intervene. In the contractual scenarios discussed above – contractual relationships between private parties and consumer relationships and so on – the level of uncertainty is low. In the former, formalism might have a stronger role than in the latter case (consumer cases), where contextualism is marked. In both situations, however, mitigating uncertainty is not the central concern: the relationships tend to deal with reasonably defined performance expected from the parties.

These cases by no means, however, exhaustively describe the low-level of sophistication of the economy. A third identifiable pattern includes cases of contractual collaboration involving high levels of uncertainty and, indeed, innovation (as in the case, for instance, of the famed Indian *jugaad* economy). They present complex forms of governance to sustain cooperative equilibria and an almost complete absence of formal enforcement but, instead, an often surprisingly stable system of relational enforcement. These cases have mostly been chronicled in the context of the “informal sector” of the developing world, but also exist in many pockets of the advanced industrial west.

As Radjou, Prabhu and Ahuja describe in the context of India's famed *jugaad* economy, these sectors are often exemplars in the art of improvisation or frugal innovation, or “overcoming harsh constraints by improvising an effective solution using limited resources.”¹⁴⁴ Key to the success of

¹⁴² HL Ross & NO Littlefield, *Complaint as a Problem-Solving Mechanism*, 12 LAW SOC. REV. 199 (1978).

¹⁴³ POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS DO PODER JUDICIÁRIO - OS MAIORES LITIGANTES EM AÇÕES CONSUMERISTAS: MAPEAMENTO E PROPOSIÇÕES, (2018).

¹⁴⁴ N Radjou, J Prabhu & S Ahuja, *Use Jugaad to Innovate Faster, Cheaper, Better*, HARV. BUS. REV. (2011).

this enterprise is a framework based on deep knowledge and experience. The authors stress four factors, in particular, thrift and inclusivity, but even more importantly bottom-up participation or collaboration and flexibility or adaptability. But almost every region of the Global South has an equivalent term, in francophone Africa it is called *l'économie de la débrouillardise*, or literally the economy of resourcefulness—or, simply, System D.¹⁴⁵ The overall size of this sector is not small: according to many estimates, it employs 1.8 billion people and has a turnover of \$10 trillion.

Indeed, these situations often emerge where the legal system fails to include a number of individuals or communities in market practices vital to their survival. In response, a different system emerges—often against or ignored by the law—as a means of economic survival for these individuals. For instance, communities of people might not have access to credit, to housing, to transport routes, to trade, because the formal system imposes entry barriers or threshold requirements for their participation in the respective schemes that cannot be met. Hence, parallel systems emerge in the “shadow of the law”, with different threshold requirements that might allow these citizens to participate and have access to these basic services. As De Soto, ironically a champion of formalization, reports extra-legal systems are created to structure the housing of poor communities, developed in marginal neighbourhoods in Peru, in the shadow of the legal system.¹⁴⁶ Acquisition contracts and informal associations of different kinds are created to organize the illegal occupation of lands that were invaded or acquired from parties about to be expropriated. The same prevails in relation to transport and trade, where complex activities, outside the law, are organized through different mechanisms involving the collaboration and joint participation of the different parties involved.

In some situations, contracts might not even be necessary to regulate the relationship. In a seminal empirical case study conducted in California, Ellickson found that rural inhabitants in Shasta County resolve disputes with their neighbors regarding escaped cattle with no regard at all to the applicable legal rules. Instead, they create informal norms or apply social norms to solve their disputes, as well as privately adjudicate their disputes, beyond the law.¹⁴⁷ The most persuasive tranche of empirical evidence that exists in this regard is the extensive database on common pool resources assembled by Ostrom.¹⁴⁸ In these situations, uncertainty stems from the inherent variability in the relationship. In these cases involving scarcity of resources, the mechanisms created by the parties often cannot establish, *ex ante*, for instance, the quantity of

¹⁴⁵ R NEUWIRTH, *STEALTH OF NATIONS: THE GLOBAL RISE OF THE INFORMAL ECONOMY* (Reprint edition ed. 2012).

¹⁴⁶ H DE SOTO, *THE OTHER PATH : THE INVISIBLE REVOLUTION IN THE THIRD WORLD* (1989).

¹⁴⁷ RC ELICKSON, *ORDER WITHOUT LAW* (1994).

¹⁴⁸ E OSTROM, *GOVERNING THE COMMONS: THE EVOLUTION OF INSTITUTIONS FOR COLLECTIVE ACTION* (1990).

water that a certain member of the common pool can withdraw in *Huerta* irrigation institutions in Spain; or how much fish a fisherman can extract from a certain spot without causing depletion of resources in Alanya, Turkey; or how many cows a farmer from Torbel, Switzerland can send to Swiss meadows during the winter without causing overgrazing. Rather, what is observed is the creation of certain procedures, adapted to local circumstances, developed through the course of a long period of trial and error-based experimentation, allowing for some flexibility in the determination of the adequate level of use of resources. Therefore, in Spanish *Huertas*, different rules for extraction of water have been designed, considering availability of resources, and establishing allocation tied to the ownership of land (sometimes creating a period of availability for extraction of water), or sometimes creating a market for buying rights of extraction.¹⁴⁹ Fisheries have created a rotating system where all fisherman rotate in their spots to make sure all have the same opportunities to benefit in Alanya.¹⁵⁰ The number of cows that each farmer can send to the Swiss meadows is connected to the number of animals they can feed during the winter.¹⁵¹ In most of these cases, a key similarity is “that all face uncertain and complex environments”.¹⁵² There is a procedure and a private court created by the parties to undertake the resolution of disputes and sometimes to revise the existing rules in case of need. The involved parties participate in the establishment of these institutions.

For instance, in the instance of the global microfinance industry, Haldar and Stiglitz found exceptionally high levels of compliance have been recorded without resort to formal enforcement, but backed on a highly context-specific system based on peer monitoring and strong social bonds.¹⁵³ Entering a domain that had long been written off by mainstream economics as a chronic market failure, credit markets in rural regions of the developing world, microfinance went on to become one of the most successful credit institutions in global history. Despite its focus on small loans, the worldwide scale of the initiative was anything but small: at the peak of its success, it boasted a lending base of 1 billion and penetration of some of the most hard-to-reach parts of the globe. Moreover, it consistently reported repayment rates in the region of 98 per cent, significantly higher than that of most conventional banks. Most remarkably of all, these metrics were achieved without any formal lending contracts whatsoever or, indeed, any collateral. The key to its success was the removal of the institutional barriers that kept a large majority of the world population excluded from formal lending markets and its replacement with

¹⁴⁹ *Id.* at 69–88.

¹⁵⁰ *Id.* at 19–20.

¹⁵¹ *Id.* at 61–65.

¹⁵² *Id.* at 88.

¹⁵³ A Haldar & JE Stiglitz, *Group Lending, Joint Liability, and Social Capital*, 44 *POLIT. SOC.* 459–497 (2016).

a kind of implicit contract embedded in the community (via the novel group lending mechanism that it employed). This alternative institutional mechanism was not only more economical (thereby reducing the cost of credit), but significantly better adapted to the local contexts and the product of an intricate process of empirical experimentation. Similar phenomena have been observed in the context of producers' cooperatives or for schemes of rotating savings, organized through non-market institutions, backed by social ties, and successful without the need for formal enforcement.¹⁵⁴

What is of note here are the striking similarities between the procedures created in many of these cases with the ones that are employed in high level of uncertainty in sophisticated commercial transactions, especially in the initial phase of trial and error for designing the adequate institutions.

5. Analysis

The extensive empirical evidence examined in the previous section demonstrated significant variations in contracting practices, substantiating the scepticism of theoretical legal scholarship with regard to unitary contract theory. Based on one of the most robust databases on contracting practices ever collated, combining both secondary sources and original studies undertaken by both authors, we claim not just that contracting practices and methods of contractual interpretation vary widely across jurisdictions, as long established by studies of comparative private law but that, even within a single legal system, important differences are to be found regarding contracting practices and methods of contractual interpretation. Furthermore, the variation in contracting patterns (both rules and systems of interpretation) are not only to be found in legal domains that have come to be historically segregated from the mainstream contract law, such as consumer or labour law, but within the very core of contract law: private and commercial relationships.

We propose that the relatively more recent empirical data on contracting practices represents an even more radical step in this process of disintegration of a unitary contract theory. This is clearly observable by examining how different generations of empirical studies on contracting practices evolved and how this empirical evidence has interacted with and supported the legal scholarship refuting the unitary perspective on contracts. However, these different generations of empirical studies complement rather than replace each other.

¹⁵⁴ K Munshi, *Nonmarket Institutions*, in UNDERSTANDING POVERTY (2006).

The first generation of empirical studies on contracts (initiated by Macauley)¹⁵⁵ claimed that, especially in long-term relationships, contract planning and the role of courts is very limited. Most contingencies are solved by the parties themselves, informally, supported by the business needs of continuing relationships with the counterparty and avoiding reputational damage in the market.

The second generation of empirical studies advanced to an understanding that, especially in more complex relationships, the deployment of an institutional framework was crucial to facilitate contractual collaborations, such as contract planning with different mechanisms of contract governance. In markets involving a number of actors undertaking similar kinds of transactions, industry and trade rules would create contextualizing regimes and special adjudicatory bodies for resolving disputes among them.

More recently, in what could be perhaps classified as a third generation of studies on contractual relationships, an altered reality came to be observed in the high-level of sophistication of the market economy, where companies operate in a state of constant innovation. More particularly, the strain of legal scholarship that has come to be known as braiding theory argues that formal and informal contracting interact to create a framework favourable to cooperation. In these agreements, complex mechanisms allow for the constant specification, and potential renegotiation, of the parties' obligations. More than creating a formal mechanism, contracts to innovate generate a framework of cooperation that encourage the creation of informal trust between the parties. This is a more radical development because it bridges the dichotomy between formal and relational contract theory (in the sense of Macauley's, not Macneil's, work) that has so far dominated the theory of contract. The relationship is neither based solely on the formal contract nor solely based on informal incentives and business needs: there is an interactive dynamic between the two. Supporting the position that informal incentives can be encouraged through formal means, some authors defend the view that Macauley's traditional perspective on relational theory has become outdated considering complex contractual design.

We argue that there is a missing element in this picture: that is braiding of formal and informal incentives in not limited to the frontiers of the knowledge economy but exists in many transactions in the low-level of sophistication of the market economy. The common theme in these two extreme ends of the market economy is the need to content with high levels of

¹⁵⁵ Macaulay, *supra* note 54.

uncertainty, and where it is necessary to adapt the collaboration to the specific context. The uncertainty factor inherently limits the effectiveness of the formal contractual regime.

It is our claim that this insight is significant for legal scholarship. It reveals that complex forms of contracting, mingling (or braiding) formal and informal incentives to facilitate collaboration in the market, existing both in advanced forms of cooperation (as demonstrated by braiding theory on contracting for innovation) but also in the low level of sophistication of the market economy, reveals something important about the nature of contract under conditions of extreme uncertainty: it facilitates “experimentalism”, a procedure for the constant learning and revision of the parties’ obligations in light of the accumulated knowledge.

It is particularly worthwhile comparing what similarities these kinds of transactions in the different ends of the market economy present. In our view, the unifying theme across these disparate ends is a need for a deep level of collaboration or iterative learning: the challenges created by uncertainty (in the Knightian sense)¹⁵⁶ or by the collective action problems¹⁵⁷ require an ongoing, revisable, iterative process of collaboration. In the case of innovation practices, this learning is required by the unpredictability inherent in the productive activity, which complicates the choice of the appropriate institutional model to be followed. Instead, parties develop a procedural framework to allow for the constant revision of these practices to make them appropriate to the evolving context. Once the innovative activity is finished, then a stable, more static framework can be established, but not until then. In the case of the lower end of the market economy, we claim that learning is also required by high uncertainty or complexity or ongoing dynamism of the environment, resulting in highly nimble and cost-effective informal economies.

In all these cases, trust is paramount for these relationships to be successful, but, at the same time, there is some kind of institutional foundation (that could perhaps be only loosely identified as “formal”) that supports this framework and allows trust to flourish or to be efficiently employed in a practical endeavour. There are mechanisms of constant monitoring (often, peer monitoring), constant iterative exchange of information, strong informal incentives to maintain cooperation and to prevent opportunism, and normally no (or a very low) level of formal court enforcement whatsoever, with adjudication being often undertaken privately. They could be accurately described as mechanisms that allow for the constant revision of the parties’ obligations having in view the information provided through the framework of cooperation. The formal institutions, in this case, display features far removed from traditional contract and property

¹⁵⁶ On the distinction between risk and pure uncertainty, see F KNIGHT, *RISK, UNCERTAINTY AND PROFIT* (1921).

¹⁵⁷ M OLSON, *THE LOGIC OF COLLECTIVE ACTION: PUBLIC GOODS AND THE THEORY OF GROUPS* (1971); G Hardin, *The tragedy of the commons.*, 162 *SCIENCE* 1243–1248 (1968).

rights as they are understood by the economic orthodoxy, which envisions these institutions as the sufficient legal basis to promote development.¹⁵⁸

This position is slowly starting to percolate into economic scholarship. Indeed, a very new paper by Frydlinger, Hart and Vitasek (2019) entitled “A New Approach to Contracts”—albeit new only in the economics discourse—borrows heavily from legal thought and makes the case for “formal relational contracts”. Drawing on the Dell-FedEx contract and a database of 57 other companies, including Intel, AstraZeneca, the Swedish telecommunications firm, Telia and the Canadian government, they advocate for contracts that are legally enforceable but with an explicit focus on the relationship between the partners and elements like a shared vision, guiding principles and governance structures. They extol the virtues of the Japanese idea of *Keiretsu*—of which Toyota (discussed at length above) and Nissan are examples—in which buyers form close associations with, and often own stakes, in suppliers.¹⁵⁹ This incipient acceptance of a broader paradigm of contracts within economics, and engagement with the legal position is a good sign. As Hart puts it, “Economists are drawn to areas with simple, elegant, uncontroversial models. The area of incomplete contracts is not like that; it is messy. But contracts are incomplete in reality and contractual incompleteness underlies numerous significant phenomena, some of which have great policy relevance.”¹⁶⁰ Indeed, trust and informality were often ignored by economists because they were considered relics of underdeveloped economic systems. It turns out, however, that trust is not only an artifice of traditional economic systems, but crucial to the very frontiers of economic development.

6. Conclusion

In this article, we challenged the single, unitary concept of contract that is assumed by most economic theories to underpin efficient collaboration in the market economy. This critique of the dominant approach in economics is based on a theory of contracts now standard, and indeed with a long-established genealogy, in legal scholarship. The understanding of contracts in law has long acknowledged that different legal systems, even within capitalist market economies, are likely to apply the same general, abstract principles in different ways – displaying, for instance, a range of approaches to striking the balance between freedom of contract and solidarity. In other words, the extent to which courts will take into consideration the formal agreement itself might

¹⁵⁸ NORTH, *supra* note 17.

¹⁵⁹ Frydlinger, Hart, and Vitasek, *supra* note 20.

¹⁶⁰ O Hart, *Incomplete Contracts and Control*, 107 AM. ECON. REV. 1731–1752, 1749 (2017).

vary greatly and will more often than not take account of a range of contextual variables. Furthermore, a recent turn taken by legal scholarship has mounted a critique even more radical than the standard legal concept of contracts: bringing into question whether a unified theory of contracts is at all possible, given the dizzying range of exclusions, exceptions and repressions that marked legal evolution of Contract law.

We begin by observing how much more nuanced the legal concept of contracts is relative to the economic one, but our claim goes beyond that. We make the case that, even within a single legal system, starkly different contracting practices and forms of applying Contract law are related to the level of sophistication of the market economy, or the tier, to which the relevant relationship pertains. We examine an extensive database of empirical literature demonstrating that, in fact, the level of contract planning, the efficiency of relational incentives to generate voluntary compliance and the level of legal enforcement will vary significantly on the basis of a range of contextual factors, not least the tier of the economy within which the collaboration is located. Finally, we offer the novel insight that there are significant similarities, so far largely unnoticed in contract theory literature, between contracting practices in the high and the low levels of sophistication of the market economy. This insight not only makes the case for conducting a rigorous comparative study of the similarities between the two sectors with a view to understanding how better to regulate them, but, indeed, helps clarify the nature of the contract itself.

Our central point is that these variations and divergences in contracting practices and methods of contract interpretation are not to be feared. They do not undermine contract theory, nor do they represent a radical departure from it. Indeed, the evolution of these new types of contract have often supported the most innovative types of collaborations, ranging of the highly complex and novel collaborations of the “new economy” at the cutting-edge of technological innovation to the tremendously cost-effective practices of “frugal innovation”. We claim that just as the empirical literature displays the relational, fluid and dynamic nature of these practices on the ground, the quicker we are able to widen our theoretical taxonomy the better we will be able to understand, explain and support these exciting phenomena.

In embracing this pluralism, there may be something for economics to learn from legal theory.

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